

D4.2 Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation and support of territorial RRI through Citizen Science strategies within S3 priorities

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Summary

The European TRANSFORM project brings together three European regions (Lombardy, Brussels Capital and Catalonia) to experiment with different innovative participatory methodologies. The objective: to make their research and innovation (R&I) activities and policies more accountable and aligned with societal needs by applying the principles of "Responsible Research and Innovation" (RRI).

Specifically, the Catalan cluster experiments with the citizen science methodology, with the aim of demonstrating the benefits it can bring in transforming the way policies are made and thereby developing policies that are more aligned with citizens' needs, concerns and aspirations. The main objective is to integrate citizen science into Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy, to advance more effectively towards a greener, digital, more resilient and fairer socioeconomic model.

To this end, two main activities have been carried out: 1) the setting up of a Think Tank on RRI and citizen science composed of different stakeholders from the regional R&I ecosystem; 2) the co-design (together with the members of the Think Tank) and implementation of 2 citizen science pilots: one in the field of waste, other in the field of health.

After 3 years of the project, this process has had several positive impacts at local and regional level, which deserve to be shared publicly so that other regions can take advantage of the lessons learned to implement similar processes. Firstly, the processes carried out in the citizen science pilots had fostered the transformation of the local policy-making cycle towards more responsible approaches, integrating the voice of citizens and other territorial actors. Secondly, the results of the citizen science pilots are being taken into account for the development of future local policies that are more aligned with social needs. Thirdly, RRI and citizen science have been integrated in RIS3CAT 2030 and some of the funding programmes and strategies that are developed within this framework. Finally, the Think Tank member organisations (both those participating in the implementation of the pilots and those not) have increased their knowledge on RRI and citizen science and learnt first-hand about the practical benefits of applying citizen science in R&I projects.

Both the process and the impacts and lessons learned from the TRANSFORM Catalan cluster are explained in this document.

Chapter 1, “The framework: the final goal of TRANSFORM” contextualises the TRANSFORM project and its main objectives.

Chapter 2, “The Catalan cluster”, briefly describes the objectives, activities and expected impacts of the Catalan cluster within TRANSFORM, as well as contains a brief description of the partners involved.

Chapter 3, “The selected methodology: citizen science”, explains the methodology implemented, citizen science, and the main current challenges faced by the sector in informing public policy.

Chapter 4, “Regional context in which the methodology has been applied”, contextualises the state of RRI in the R&I ecosystem in Catalonia at the beginning of the project.

Chapter 5, “Activities carried out”, explains in detail all the activities carried out by the Catalan cluster (creation of the Think Tank and implementation of the two citizen science pilots).

Chapter 6, “Impact in the region”, describes the short-term impacts generated by the activities, both at local and regional level, and which are related to the impacts expected at the beginning of the project. It also describes the long-term impacts that can be envisaged (beyond TRANSFORM) and the actions that the Catalan cluster is taking to make them happen.

In chapter 7, “Reflections on the potential of citizen science for shared agendas: learnings from the TRANSFORM project”, the Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds (Catalan Government) expresses the reflections that the TRANSFORM project has generated on the potential of citizen science for the development of shared agendas, which are the main drivers guiding Catalonia towards a greener, more digital, more resilient and fairer socioeconomic model.

In chapter 8, “Challenges and recommendations to co-design and implement transformative citizen science projects”, the Catalan cluster shares the main challenges it has faced in implementing transformative citizen science projects, and practical recommendations for other regions willing to undertake this type of processes.

TRANSFORM

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1. The framework: the final goal of TRANSFORM

As expressed in the Grant Agreement, “in TRANSFORM three European regions join forces and open up their R&I activities to **co-create more responsible approaches to innovation**. Lombardy in Italy, Brussels in Belgium and Catalonia in Spain are all leaders in experimenting new pathways for territorial development. TRANSFORM brings them together to design, test and disseminate three sound co-creation methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting; design for social innovation; and citizen science). These frameworks will be **at the forefront of implementation of Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3)**. They provide approaches and application areas of responsible and accountable territorial development through **new forms of local decision-making**. They have also proven beneficial in aligning science, innovation and society, **making R&D more responsive to citizens’ needs, concerns and aspirations**. The three initiatives will implement a mutual learning process within and beyond Europe, pairing with a parallel co-design exercise in Boston (Massachusetts, US). The work in these three clusters will **support and increase co-creation and participatory processes within their R&I ecosystems**, both building on existing regional commitments towards transformative opportunities and strengthen the opening effect on the organisations involved. **Regional governments involved in TRANSFORM will reflect on, experiment with, learn from and adopt RRI approaches to their R&I policies and actions.**”

Thus, the main goal of TRANSFORM is for regional governments to see the potential of these participatory methodologies to make the R&I political decision-making process more responsible; and to incorporate Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in their regional policies (RIS3CAT, in the case of Catalonia). To this end, each of the regional clusters applies a methodology with the aim of demonstrating the benefits it can bring in transforming the way policies are made and thereby developing policies that are more aligned with citizens' needs, concerns and aspirations.

2. The Catalan cluster

One of the main objectives of the Catalan cluster is to explore how to integrate citizen science into Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy, to advance more effectively towards a greener, digital, more resilient and fairer socioeconomic model.

2.1 *Objectives, activities, and expected impacts*

The objectives of the Catalan cluster in TRANSFORM are the following:

- To foster the incorporation of **participatory strategies and citizen science in the RIS3CAT**, its instruments, and the "business as usual" of the organisations within the R&I ecosystem.
- To develop **multi-stakeholder working models incorporating quadruple helix stakeholders**.
- To shift **novel and transparent governance relationships** within the R&I policy making cycle.

To achieve these objectives, the Catalan TRANSFORM cluster has developed two main activities:

- The setting up of a **Think Tank on RRI and citizen science** composed of different stakeholders from the regional R&I ecosystem, with the aim that participating organisations increase their knowledge on RRI and citizen science as well as their capacities to implement this perspective in their own strategies and projects.
- The **co-design (together with the members of the Think Tank) and implementation of 2 citizen science pilots**, with the aim of, on the one hand, transforming the local R&I policy-making cycle to more responsible approaches through citizen science and, on the other hand, serving as demonstration pilots with a view to the incorporation and

promotion of citizen science by the Catalan Government through RIS3CAT and its instruments.

The Think Tank has provided a meeting place and a forum to discuss the challenges and the potential of citizen science to address societal challenges. Through the 2 pilot projects the Catalan cluster has experimented and generated new knowledge, methodologies and evidence about how researchers, public administrations and citizens can work together to address those challenges that really matter.

Consequently, the Catalan cluster activities expected to have several **impacts within the development of TRANSFORM (short term)**:

- Local impact 1: that the **process carried out in the citizen science pilots fosters the transformation of the local policy-making cycle** towards more responsible approaches, integrating the voice of citizens and other territorial actors.
- Local impact 2: that the **results of the citizen science pilots are taken into account** for the development of future policies that are more aligned with social needs.
- Regional impact 1: that **RRI and citizen science are integrated in RIS3CAT 2030** and some of the funding programmes and strategies that are developed within this framework.
- Regional impact 2: that **Think Tank member organisations** (both those participating in the implementation of the pilots and those not) **increase their knowledge on RRI and citizen science** and learn first-hand about the practical benefits of applying citizen science in R&I projects.

Figure 1. Activities, outcomes and expected impacts of the Catalan cluster within TRANSFORM

Although it is not possible to determine the impact of TRANSFORM's activities in the long term (nor is the monitoring of this impact considered a task within the project), it is possible to envision expected impacts beyond the project (long term).

- **Local impact:** that the organisations that have participated in the development of the citizen science pilots incorporate this methodology in the development of future projects aimed at tackling socio-environmental challenges through R&I.
- **Regional impact:** that the organisations participating in the Catalan Think Tank and others within the Catalan R&I ecosystem incorporate citizen science as a means of integrating RRI within its future R&I projects and strategies.

2.2 Member profiles

The Catalan cluster is composed by the following organisations:

2.2.1 Science for Change, the cluster leader and citizen science expert:

Science for Change (SfC) is a SME born from the will to tackle societal and environmental challenges affecting communities using innovative solutions. SfC specialises in developing user-centred, innovative services and products based on citizen science, participatory strategies, community engagement and co-creation processes to facilitate social innovation.

It uses a methodology based on a quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement, to promote dialogue, increase transparency, and to co-design innovative solutions that are relevant to all the stakeholders involved.

Role: SfC is the leader of the Catalan cluster (WP4. Citizen Science in RIS3 - Catalonia Region). One of its functions is to coordinate the different activities of the cluster (Think Tank and pilot projects), guaranteeing cooperation and information between the different members of the cluster and leading the design and execution of the activities and their contents. In this aspect, it is also in charge of leading the dissemination and communication of the project's activities and outputs, mobilising the other members of the cluster and other possible agents that work as multipliers (members of the Think Tank, among others). On the other hand, Science for Change also manages the coordination of the Catalan cluster with the rest of the project's clusters, with the aim of aligning the evolution of all the clusters in their territorial activities and above all in those activities that imply a global perspective of inter-cluster work.

2.2.2 The Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds¹ of the Catalan Government. Regional policy maker

The Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds (SEAEF) is the unit in the Catalan Government responsible for the coordination and the monitoring of Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3CAT). Within this framework of action, SEAEF work on the integration of RRI dimensions (Anticipation, Reflexivity, Inclusion and Responsiveness) in RIS3CAT through:

- The entrepreneurial discovery process: bottom-up approaches in which government, companies, the universities, research and innovation players and civil society (hereafter referred to quadruple-helix stakeholders) identify areas of specialisation in the territory and then design and implement programmes, actions and projects to promote them.
- Shared agendas for sustainability and social change: to articulate the collective action of various stakeholders aimed at addressing a common complex challenge and the

¹ In March 2022 the Catalan Government created the Secretariat of Economic Affairs and European Funds and the Area of Economic Strategy. This area has assumed all the competences related to Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy.

problems that this challenge may generate. Shared agendas are articulated in three steps:

- Understand systemic challenges and prepare the basis for collective action.
- Co-design, test and disseminate new solutions to the problems identified through multi-stakeholder transformative-shared agendas.
- Reproduce and amplify the solutions tested to transform the system.

In the new programming period (2021-2030), the aim of SEAEF is to go a step further by integrating the RRI dimensions in the RIS3CAT, with a strong focus on:

- Developing and testing methodologies and tools designed to enhance the participation of quadruple-helix players, especially the participation of civil society, to promote “R&I with society and for society”.
- Generating new narratives, frameworks and monitoring tools for RRI.

TRANSFORM is a crucial project for the SEAEF in order to better experiment, understand and apply citizen science to public policies.

The role that the SEAEF plays within the Catalan cluster and in the global TRANSFORM project is summarised as:

- To guide and facilitate the project framework so that the objectives are aligned with those of the Catalan ecosystem and its governance (That is achieved by connecting stakeholders, proposing relevant trends and being actively involved in development).
- To be inspired by the evolution of the results of the Catalan cluster to influence the RIS3CAT and adapt visions and public policies (this is done by involving, training and connecting decisive stakeholders of the public administration, academia and relevant companies).
- To learn with and from other regional clusters of TRANSFORM.

2.2.3 OpenSystems from University of Barcelona. Experienced research group in citizen science

OpenSystems UB is a multidisciplinary group founded in 2012 of the University of Barcelona (UB) that focuses on public participation as a core element of the way of doing science. The

group is a leading research group in Spain, Catalonia and Barcelona contexts on the emerging field of citizen science. The group also belongs to the Universitat de Barcelona Institute of Complex Systems (UBICS) and the Complexity Lab Barcelona. OpenSystems works together with many actors and builds tailored-made research collectives to address concerns mostly grounded in urban contexts. The group has expertise in co-creating citizen science projects, in the subsequent data gathering, data interpretation and data analysis processes especially when it includes human behaviour and social issues. Citizen science main issues of UB lie within the so-called citizen social science and within the scopes of data science, complex systems science and social science.

Role: Within the Catalan cluster, UB contributes to the development of citizen science methodologies. More particularly, UB has been moderating one of the groups in the several workshops. In this context, UB has been contributing to the analysis of the citizen science practices inside the RRI framework. UB is also providing insights in the co-creation process. UB has also been focussed on the academics' perspective to bring citizen science in the Catalan Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3). UB has a key role in the design and development of the co-designed citizen science pilots. UB also expects to deliver scientific results jointly with the rest of cluster partners (specially SfC) that provides evidence on the positive contribution.

3. The selected methodology: citizen science

The methodology chosen by the Catalan cluster to experiment with has been citizen science, due to the potential it has as a tool to generate, together with citizens, valid information for public policies and, in turn, provide benefits at a social level such as the promotion of a more informed and responsible citizenry and the development of a new governance model for R&I.

However, the link between citizen science and public policy does not usually occur, which is why TRANSFORM represents an opportunity to demonstrate that this link is possible and that it brings countless benefits.

“For a long time now, Science for Change has been making a huge effort to develop citizen science projects that have an impact on public policy. The data should not remain in a drawer within the research group but have a real impact. The possibility of working in a cluster directly with the regional administration was a perfect opportunity.”

Diana Reinoso. Project manager at Science for Change

“Our aim in participating in TRANSFORM is that citizen science should not only be an initiative of the academic world, but also involve other social actors (municipalities, research groups that are not our own, public health agencies, the citizens themselves as a group "affected", etc.). Making more extensive use of citizen science.

For us, citizen science is not only useful to collect data, but also to "leverage" active policies based on evidence and to co-define projects with many other actors outside academia.”

Josep Perelló. Founding Director OpenSystemsUB

3.1 What is citizen science?

It is a way of doing science in which citizens are invited to participate in one or multiple phases of the scientific process, from the definition of the research question to the analysis of results, including the choice of method and the data collection.

Citizen science is a way to do science that aims, on the one hand, to ensure that scientific projects are linked to social needs and, on the other, to increase citizens' knowledge of and trust in science. Citizen science has also been posited as an alternative way of generating data that might not otherwise exist. In some cases, it has sought to establish citizens as experts in the field, given that they have specific knowledge based on their everyday life experience.

The [Green Paper on Citizen Science](#) describes it as:

‘the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers. While adding value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills, and deeper understanding of the scientific work in an appealing way. As a result of this open, networked and trans-disciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved leading to more democratic research based on evidence-informed decision making arising from the scientific method, in whole or in part, by amateur or non-professional scientists.’

For a project to be considered citizen science it must comply with the [10 Principles of Citizen Science](#) defined by the European Citizen Science Association ([ECSA](#)) and take into account the conclusions of the report [Characteristics of Citizen Science](#) (ECSA).

3.2 Ten principles of citizen science

As described in the [10 principles of citizen science](#), “Citizen science is a flexible concept which can be adapted and applied within diverse situations and disciplines. The statements below were developed by the ‘Sharing best practice and building capacity’ working group of the European Citizen Science Association, led by the Natural History Museum London with input from many members of the Association, to set out some of the key principles which as a community we believe underlie good practice in citizen science.”

1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavours that generate new knowledge or understanding. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.

2. Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.
3. Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy.
4. Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process. This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.
5. Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.
6. Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for. However unlike traditional research approaches, citizen science provides opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science.
7. Citizen science project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open access format. Data sharing may occur during or after the project, unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.
8. Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.
9. Citizen science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.
10. The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities

3.3 The importance of stakeholder engagement in Citizen Science

Public engagement is considered one of the main factors for reaching greater alignment of research with the local context. Nonetheless, stakeholder's participation in science cannot

be taken for granted². As Citizen Science projects and initiatives are emerging in current days as policymakers, citizens and scientists see the value of conducting research in this way, understanding the specificities that influence people to participate in citizen science and the factors to continue participating are crucial. If we understand citizen science as the partnering of scientists with citizens to answer scientific questions, then, strategies for recruiting and retaining diverse stakeholders becomes a crucial part of this equation³.

Stakeholders can be involved in citizen science in several ways, including co-designing projects and research questions, suggesting proposals based on results, data collection, sorting, analysing data, and communicating results and findings.

The National Coordination Center for Public Engagement defines public engagement as “the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit” (National Coordination Center for Public Engagement n.d.).

From a historical perspective -albeit brief- the term engagement was introduced into our language with the transition from the called *deficit model* of science communication to the *dialogue model* and finally to the *participative model*.

Another framework is the one that establishes the *levels of engagement*⁴ in citizen science projects, which defines the different levels of citizen participation in citizen science projects, taking into account as a variable the phase(s) of the scientific process in which citizens participate. Of course, in any citizen science project, different profiles of citizens can be defined to participate in different phases, from the point of view of flexibility.

² Rask et al. (2016), Innovative Public Engagement, PE2020 Project, d’Andrea L., Caiati G. (2016), Toolkit on Public Engagement with Science, PE2020 Project.

³ Dickinson, J.L., Phillips, T.B., Purcell, K. and Shirk, J., 2012. The current state of citizen science as a tool for ecological research and public engagement. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 10(6): 291-297. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110236>.

⁴ Haklay, M. (2013). Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation. In: Sui, D., Elwood, S., Goodchild, M. (eds) *Crowdsourcing Geographic Knowledge*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

Figure 2. Levels of engagement in citizen science Haklay, M. (2013).

3.4 What benefits can citizen science bring to R&I policies?

“The proposition that science-based decisions should be reviewed by independent experts strikes us today as hardly more controversial than the proposition that there is no completely risk-free society”⁵.

Societies in Europe are more educated than ever before, enabling thousands of people to actively contribute in a wide range of R&I practices. For this reason, it is unsurprising that this form of participation in R&I, which nowadays is called “Citizen Science ” is receiving much more attention. Citizen science is one of the eight pillars of the [EU’s Open Science policy](#) and recent year participation is becoming its cornerstone. Once open data and journal open access are already consolidated, openness in science is now very much close to citizen science and its science democratisation efforts. These can be further illustrated by the fact that [LIBER](#) (Europe’s research library community) that has strongly advocated for open access to journals and data now is dedicating efforts to incorporate librarians as key mediation actors in citizen science. Also, as an example: ongoing [EU TORCH](#) project led by Universitat de Barcelona is a university alliance that explores new venues for the university of the future

⁵ Jasanoff, S., “The Fifth Branch: science advisers as policy makers (Cambridge, Mass. and London: Harvard University Press, 1990) p.1.

with a focus on pressing issues: climate change, sustainability, gender gap, inclusion and equity. Within TORCH, Open science and citizen science are being identified as key elements to facilitate universities transformation.

Very general motivation from research agencies to further promote citizen science can be taken from a quote by the [European Research Area](#): “The general public should be able to make significant contributions and be recognized as valid European science knowledge producers”⁶. Research agencies worldwide (at a global and at a local scale) are indeed putting great expectations on citizen science. They see in citizen science a way to generate the “right” (and new) data to address societal challenges with at least the involvement of the general public but also with the potential to share this effort with civil society organisations or the private sector⁷. Public agencies also see in citizen science a way to co-produce knowledge which can be faster transformed into actions and policies⁸; and this is often framed within what is being called sustainability transitions⁹ and the rationale behind hypothesises participation and a shared effort as an effective way to faster commit societal challenges. It is thus not surprising that citizen science calls within the last Horizon 2020 emphasises the need to deliver policy briefs related to a set of evidence gathered with the public.

It is however true that citizen science is still young and it is not an institutionalised practice yet. It is still unclear how research performing organisations and public administrations can join forces in this endeavour and this is what motivates the need to run pilots to demonstrate its potential with successful stories.

In relation to Research and Innovation policies, pilots embracing citizen science can boost:

⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en#the-eus-open-science-policy

⁷ See for instance: Irwin, A. (2018). No PhDs needed: how citizen science is transforming research. *Nature*, 562(7726), 480-483. / Derrick, G., & Hettrick, S. (2022). Time to celebrate science's hidden contributors. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00454-3>

⁸ For global policy see for instance: Fritz, S., See, L., Carlson, T., Haklay, M. M., Oliver, J. L., Fraisl, D., ... & West, S. (2019). Citizen science and the United Nations sustainable development goals. *Nature Sustainability*, 2(10), 922-930.)

⁹ See for instance: Sauermaann, H., Vohland, K., Antoniou, V., Balázs, B., Göbel, C., Karatzas, K., ... & Winter, S. (2020). Citizen science and sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 49(5), 103978.)

- Relevance and effectiveness of the research **aligned with societal challenges**, especially to those issues which are becoming urgent and on which we must share uncertainties with citizens and all stakeholders. Some experts have claimed here for a **socially robust knowledge** and there is an increasing effort to invite citizens or civil society that can raise their own concerns in appropriate spaces that help to spark innovative research avenues and set research agendas. Of course, public administrations also need to be part of this effort because they are those responsible to do it.
- Ensures the needs and values of the society, taking into account the citizens' concerns. Citizen science is also seen as a way to listen to citizens' concerns and citizen science can thus enable citizens or groups of citizens in a vulnerable situation. Citizen science can provide the strategies to better articulate the discourse of these groups and better approach an actionable knowledge and deliver recommendations grounded on scientific evidence.
- Creativity and a better quality of research. The research itself increases its quality thanks to a inter- and trans-disciplinary perspective where citizens and policymakers are part of the research as in-the-field competent experts. Their involvement enriches the research and favours an actionable knowledge which is indeed a current hot discussion in the prestigious European Research Council.
- Transparency in the research process and in the decision-making processes can be enhanced with citizen science practices. Not all citizen science projects share data but the citizen science that will be contributing in this context must follow all eight Open Science pillars.
- Science literacy and scientific education for all stakeholders is fundamental to align interests, strategies, terminology and most importantly to raise consensus. Participation in a citizen science project can be also understood as a way for citizens to better understand and to better reflect on scientific processes and scientific outcomes on key issues. Scientific literacy can in turn help to promote public discussion grounded on shared and consensuated scientific evidence and thus improve democratic quality of our societies.
- Confidence of the public in science and in public institutions can be favoured by opening up a public discussion which in turn can be triggered with a citizen science project that is transparent, accountable, and responds to citizen needs.

But citizen science is a challenging endeavour, posing complexities at all phases of implementation. However, the most relevant one for the TRANSFORM project is the policy impact.

3.5 What are the challenges for citizen science to be integrated in R&I policies?

In the interface of science-policy, the scientific evidence for **policy happens at the end of the project, usually when the funding period is over**, hence, extremely difficult to measure.

This usually happens due to a mismatch between citizen science and policy questions, times and aims. As most projects, they have a short-live, and the data generated may be stored in a repository or website without being used by any public institution. And scientists usually do not know how to integrate citizen-generated data in official databases. Besides, engaging policy makers in a citizen science project is tricky. **Project design must first think on which governance level the project may be most interested in**, e.g. In Spain health issues are legislated at the regional level, therefore, it is more convenient to engage with regional policy makers than any others. In this regard, **projects need to be well-contextualised and adapted**, and given the complexity of policy formulations, the analysis of citizen science approaches requires breaking them down into small pieces in order to truly understand the different components, impacts and possible levels of intervention.

Overall, citizen science projects can be influential at any stage of the policy process (from policy recommendations, policy analysis, to policy formulation), a recent report in 2021 by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission¹⁰ considered policy impacts as one of the most important outcomes of a citizen science project. Luckily, the citizen science ecosystem has already identified the policy benefits of this field to inform evidence-based policies aligned with societal interests, and **policy makers noted and started to support citizen science practices since it is a key element to tackle local and regional societal challenges**. Unfortunately, the overall potential of citizen science remains largely unknown for most policy makers at all governance levels.

¹⁰ Manzoni, M., Vohland K., Schade, S, Survey on Citizen Science Strategies and Initiatives: report on outcomes in Europe: Technical Report on Outcomes, European Commission, Ispra, 2021, JRC123471.

3.6 One issue in particular: the need for more support from public administrations

Institutional backing and support to promote citizen science is **one of the best ways of strengthening its practice and mainstreaming citizen science** and its sustainability over time. Building on the expertise and investments made up to date (from Horizon 2020, Open Science policies to more regional and local efforts) is crucial, but requires planning the investments carefully. As said, citizen science is a challenging endeavour that tackles many aspects of the research process, and therefore, needs dedicated attention: From strengthening networks, reinforcing training and capacity building efforts, helping overcome institutional barriers, pushing academic recognition, organising academic events with and for the general public, and facilitating data infrastructures among others.

Despite the European support to the practice of citizen science, among the 11 European participating countries in the Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) on citizen science¹¹, 4 did not have any specific national citizen science observatory and network, and the remaining ones have been created recently¹². Regarding the funding national opportunities, approximately two thirds of the countries do not have specific calls for citizen science, which means that these projects need to compete with other types of research projects, and/or having to reach alternative sources for securing funding¹³.

This MLE finalises with a set of recommendations from public institutions to the practice of citizen science by stressing the **importance of continuing funding dedicated citizen science projects**.

Overall, they are the funding agencies and public institutions, either at local, regional, national or European levels that have the responsibility of supporting citizen science

¹¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Arias, R., *Mutual learning exercise on citizen science initiatives : policy and practice. Second topic challenge paper, Ensuring good practices and impacts : Horizon Europe policy support facility*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/17212>

¹² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Haklay, M., Radicchi, A., *Mutual learning exercise on citizen science initiatives : policy and practice. Second thematic report, Ensuring good practices and impacts*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/389967> p.41.

¹³ Ibidem p.42.

initiatives to gather new scientific evidence aligned with societal needs in times of crisis. Being in the form of fundings, supporting networks, or boosting the recognition of this practice at the institutional level. TRANSFORM contributes to this process by providing evidence for policy-makers and other stakeholders of the benefits of applying citizen science and fostering its integration in the entrepreneurial discovery processes promoted by Smart Specialisation strategies.

4. Regional context in which the methodology has been applied

For the 2014-2020 period, the European Union called on all regions to draw up and implement regional innovation strategies for smart specialisation (RIS3 strategies), co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). The objective of RIS3 strategies is to focus the economic and knowledge specialisation of regions (based on their resources, strengths and capabilities) and to promote action plans providing public support for innovation to strengthen the competitiveness of the territory and foster more sustainable and inclusive growth.

RIS3 strategies are based on open innovation models in which, besides companies, research and innovation actors and governments, citizens must also be present, as they are the main beneficiaries and users of innovations. This is particularly important in a context in which new responses to the great economic, social and environmental challenges necessarily entail changes in behaviour at both individual and societal scale.

The RIS3 strategy for Catalonia (RIS3CAT) was approved in 2014. The RIS3CAT Action Plan had a budget of more than 400 million euros from the ERDF to promote innovation in the sectors defined as priorities in Catalonia. This sum was used to cofinance projects and investments worth more than 1,000 million euros in total.

RIS3CAT 2014-2020 had four strategic objectives:

- To enhance the competitiveness of the business fabric by improving the efficiency of production processes, promoting internationalisation and reorienting established sectors towards activities with greater added value.
- To promote new emerging economic activities through research, creativity and innovation in order to create and exploit new market niches.
- To consolidate Catalonia as a European knowledge hub and connect the country's technological and creative capabilities with both sectors that already exist in the territory and those that may emerge.
- To make global improvements to the Catalan system of innovation, improving the competitiveness of companies, particularly SMEs, and orienting public policies towards the promotion of innovation, internationalisation and entrepreneurship.

RIS3CAT 2014-2020 focused on seven sectoral areas of specialisation and facilitating technologies that would help Catalonia to make the transition to a more competitive, sustainable and inclusive economic model.

- Food
- Energy and resources
- Industrial systems
- Design-based industries
- Industries related to sustainable mobility
- Health Industries
- Cultural and experience-based industries

RIS3CAT combines traditional instruments for supporting research and innovation with more innovative mechanisms aimed at promoting new forms of cooperation between people and organisations to co-create public policies and innovative solutions that will enable the formulation of effective responses to the great challenges that face our society.

These new tools, the fruit of a new paradigm and a new way of understanding research and innovation (more responsible, more open, more collaborative, more transversal, etc.), often clash with the contradictions of an old paradigm that is still too present among the different quadruple helix actors. This old paradigm greatly hinders the possibility of sharing knowledge and generating methodological or procedural innovations without arousing suspicion. The contradictions between the new tools and the dominant paradigm are manifested in different areas: in regulations that restrict the implementation of projects; in the way of working; in the way of understanding collaboration; in closed-minded views about opportunities to create shared value, etc.

The R&I regional ecosystems are highly complex and disperse realities which involve a wide range of organisations and public administration programmes and strategies. At the beginning of TRANSFORM an evaluation was developed within the cluster to better understand the RIS3CAT planning and implementation (meaning its instruments, funding programmes, projects and implementing organisations) as well as its policy, societal and economic context. The aim was to have a general picture of the integration of RRI elements into the R&I ecosystem and capture the needs and possibilities to perform TRANSFORM activities to have the widest impact.

The main conclusion was that at this moment, with few exceptions, RRI as a comprehensive concept was not integrated explicitly in the main planning documents to support R&I in Catalonia. Citizen participation, however, did have more importance: it was part of the core objectives of some RIS3CAT instruments and was also mentioned at least in some public funding programmes. The main discussion was about the “quality” of the participation procedures. On the other hand, RRI has entered in the last years in the Catalan R&I ecosystem at implementation level, taking advantage of european funding programmes: many relevant actors of the Catalan R&I ecosystem, including the Catalan Government, were working on RRI projects (and also projects that highlight some of the RRI specific agendas), as SeeRRI (the Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds) and GRACE (The Agency for Management of University and Research Grants).

The field that seemed to be most advanced was health. The Health Quality and Assessment Agency of Catalonia (AQuAS) publishes the [SARIS monographs](#), reports aimed at decision-makers, professionals and non-specialized audiences with the aim of analysing current issues around health research that stimulate and encourage reflection. The collection includes a series on responsible research addressing the interaction of research with society. It has also integrated the gender and citizen participation agendas within its evaluation procedures of the research and innovation projects funded with [PERIS](#). Instead of being powerful, these examples showed that some institutions in the R&I were willing to deepen in RRI and explore its potential.

5. Activities carried out

As mentioned above, the Catalan cluster has developed two main activities to achieve its objectives. One is the setting-up of a Think Tank on RRI and citizen science. The other one is the development of two citizen science pilots together with stakeholders that were part of the Think Tank.

5.1 *The Catalan Think Tank on RRI & citizen science*

The Think Tank was conceived as a group to support the mapping, reflection process and action development of the TRANSFORM project in Catalonia, composed of as many stakeholders as possible from the R&I ecosystem interested in working with this perspective.

5.1.1 *Objectives*

Taking into account the societal, political and economic characteristics of Catalonia and its R&I ecosystem, and also the aims of the Catalan cluster, the objectives of the Think Tank were defined as:

- To contribute to the assessment of the state of RRI and citizen science in the R&I ecosystem in Catalonia.
- To define the pilots of the project
- To provide evidence of how Citizen Science can inform public agendas and strategies.
- To provide capacity building and methodology to Catalan R&I stakeholders.
- To connect policy makers with experts in Citizen Science
- To provide recommendations on how to improve the openness and inclusiveness of the regional R&I ecosystem.
- To reflect on and learn from the pilot projects and provide recommendations for RIS3CAT

5.1.2 *Organisations involved*

The different activities of the Think Tank were attended by a total of 74 representatives of 44 organisations from the triple helix of the Catalan R&I ecosystem. The diversity of the

members provided a variety of views and know-how that ensures that all societal needs are taken into account in the implementation of innovative solutions. It also represented the opportunity of increasing the overall impact of TRANSFORM beyond the project both by promoting the embedding of RRI and public participation at policy-making level and constituting the possibility of developing pilots outside TRANSFORM in other sectoral areas through additional funding.

The **criteria used to select the members** involved in the Think Tank were the following:

- key organisations of the triple helix that can reflect a sample of the existing diversity within the Catalan R&I ecosystem (meaning diversity of fields and levels of power within the government structure)
- organisations with a strong willingness in integrating RRI within their current procedures with a specific focus on transforming projects from the triple to the quadruple helix (may be organisations with or without previous experience in RRI, public participation and citizen science)
- organisations with a strong interest in participating in capacity building sessions.
- organisations related to the field of municipal waste collection and management (to develop the pilot projects within TRANSFORM)
- key members of the organisations with power to promote internal changes, develop pilot projects and/or foster RRI and public participation at policy-making level.

Think Tank attendees can be divided into two different groups:

- Key policy makers (15 representatives of 9 different departments and agencies of the Catalan Government). For example The Catalan Health Quality and Assessment Agency, the Waste Agency of Catalonia, the School of Public Administration of Catalonia, the Agency for the Management of University and Research Grants, among others.
- Implementing organisations of the Catalan R&I ecosystem (59 representatives of 35 organisations, including local public administrations, universities, research and technological centres and companies). For example, [Technological Centre for Biodiversity, Ecology, Environmental and Food Technology \(BETA, UVic-UCC\)](#), [Institute of Environmental Science and Technology \(ICTA-UAB\)](#), [CREAF - Centre for](#)

[Ecological Research and Forestry Applications](#), the company [SUEZ-AGBAR](#) and technicians from local public authorities, among others.

5.1.3 Phases

5.1.3.1 Year 2020: learning and reflecting on RRI & citizen science for the co-design of citizen science pilots

The Catalan Think Tank was launched in June 2020. From June to December 2020, the Catalan Cluster organised **4 participatory capacity building sessions on RRI and citizen science** for the members of the Think Tank. These sessions were an opportunity to exchange perspectives and views on the role and potential of citizen science to inform public policies more aligned with societal needs. One of the main topics discussed was how citizen science can contribute to articulating new forms of collaboration among academia, public administrations, companies and civil society to address the challenges that matter to society more effectively.

These webinars were conceived as a process of learning and reflection ranging from the most abstract concepts to their practical application and action; they therefore combined theoretical sections with practical and participatory sections. These webinars constituted the co-design process of the two citizen science pilots that were finally implemented.

During webinars n°1 and n°2, participants were divided in 4 thematic groups (environmental quality, waste, health, water) to develop the participatory activities. The third and fourth webinars followed a more practical approach: they were aimed at co-designing citizen science projects to address real socio-environmental challenges. Based on the interests shared by the participants, three challenges were proposed in the areas of water, health, and waste. For each challenge, a “challenge owner” was identified (public administration or company) who had to propose a real socio-environmental challenge to work on during each session.

The following table shows how the webinars led to the co-design and selection of the two citizen science pilots to be implemented.

Title	Date	Outputs
What can RRI & citizen science do for you?	Jul. 21, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveys on knowledge and opinions about RRI dimensions & CS • RRI dimensions prioritisation (by sectoral area) • Qualitative opinions about RRI aspects that should be addressed
Potential of citizen science to address social and environmental issues, increasing the impact of public policies	Sept. 21, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of possible data sets generated by citizens (by sectoral area) • List of roles of the different stakeholders in developing CS projects (by sectoral area) • List of enabling conditions for Citizen-generated data • List of enabling conditions for citizen-generated data to actually inform public policy
How to start co-designing a citizen Science project to address a socio-environmental challenge (I)	Nov. 20, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real socio-environmental challenges in the fields of health, waste and water. • Objectives and RRI dimensions to address for each challenge
How to start co-designing a citizen science project to address a socio-environmental challenge (II)	Dec. 4, 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope of the projects • Citizen generated data to be generated • Citizens to be engaged and engagement strategies

Table 1. Summary of the outputs generated in the capacity building webinars (2020)

One of the results from the four Think Tank webinars was the identification and co-design of three potential citizen science pilot projects that were relevant for the stakeholders:

- Municipal waste management.
- The problem of invisibility, underdiagnosis and lack of research into women’s diseases, specifically endometriosis.
- Restoration of riparian forests and elimination of negative impacts on river basins.

Based on the objectives of the Catalan Government and the RIS3CAT, criteria were defined in order to choose the implementation of 2 of the 3 proposed pilots.

On the one hand, municipal waste management is a very important issue for both RIS3CAT and the Catalan Waste Agency, which participates in the Think Tank. There are many initiatives led by local authorities in this field, and most of the municipalities participating in the Think Tank were interested in involving citizens in the co-design of innovative waste collection

systems. The Catalan Cluster selected Mollet local authority for the pilot project, since this municipality is participating in a RIS3CAT zero-waste initiative (shared agenda B-30) in cooperation with the Autonomous University of Barcelona. The collaboration of the municipality with the university was also a relevant factor in selecting this territory, since this collaboration opened up opportunities to engage university students in the pilot project. From the beginning, Mollet City Council local authorities and the Autonomous University of Barcelona expressed their interest in collaborating with TRANSFORM and in enhancing synergies between TRANSFORM and the RIS3CAT territorial project.

On the other hand, RIS3CAT is highly specialised in the health sector. However, there are many initiatives, but none focuses on women. Gender equality is a very relevant issue in health policies. Sant Pau Hospital and the Health Quality and Assessment Agency of Catalonia (AQuAS) participated in the 4 webinars and were from the first moment very interested in developing this pilot.

The restoration of forests is also a very relevant issue, but the interest expressed by the participants in the Think Tank was not as great as in the other two cases and for this reason it was not selected.

5.1.3.2 Year 2021: learning from & reflecting on the citizen science pilots of TRANSFORM - mid term

As a mid-term activity, taking into account that the pilots had already started to be developed, the Catalan cluster considered it appropriate to hold 2 webinars in 2021.

The first webinar was called "Citizen science as an instrument to transform public services and policies: reflection on the TRANSFORM pilots" (Nov, 11). It presented the development process of the pilots and the lessons and learnings that could be extracted at that time (said directly by the stakeholders participating in the pilots). The second webinar was called "Shared agendas and citizen science: challenges and opportunities" (Dec, 17) and dealt with citizen science as a useful tool for [Shared Agendas for sustainability and social change.](#)

5.1.3.3 Year 2022: Reflecting on the potential of citizen science transforming public policies

As the final event of the project, the [final local event will be held on 21 November](#), in which Think Tank members will be invited to attend. Other stakeholders from the R&I ecosystem will be also invited in order to increase the potential impact of TRANSFORM in the region. In this event, the process and results of the two pilots will be presented, the collaborating agents will share their experience and learnings and there will be a collective reflection on the challenges and opportunities of citizen science in Catalonia to transform public policies.

Final act of the TRANSFORM European project

25/10/2022 | 4:33 p.m

The Department of Economy and Finance, Science for Change and the University of Barcelona organize the final event of the TRANSFORM European project, which aims to introduce the principles of responsible research and innovation into the practice of public policies and the strategies for intelligent specialization (RIS3).

In Catalonia, the project has focused on mechanisms and models for citizen involvement through two citizen science pilot projects located in the territory:

- in Mollet, companies, universities and public administrations have investigated the aspects that need to be taken into account in the implementation of innovative systems for the selective collection of waste;
- at the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau, health professionals and women with endometriosis have carried out research on the experiences of the disease and the needs regarding health care.

Date: November 21, 2022
Time: from 9.45 am to 4.15 pm
Place: Palau Robert, passeig de Gràcia, 107, 08008 Barcelona
[Registration form](#)

Picture 1. Image of the invitation to the final local event of the project

5.2 Pilot 1: Citizen science for the improvement of the selective waste collection system in Mollet del Vallès

"A big part of the motivation we had was the challenge to bring about a change to the waste management model in order to have the desired levels of recycling by the EU. We like to work with the quadruple helix vision to open perspectives and make co-decisions (not only collaborating with businesses but also with the scientific field. This was a good opportunity. From the environmental field it is not usual to "open the door" to participation, now is the

opportunity not only to do "benchmarkings" and to know what they do in other cities, but to explore a solution "bottom-up", from citizenship."

Albert del Amor. Former Programme Coordinator - Area of Open Government, Economic Development and Innovation, Mollet del Vallès City Council

One of the pilot projects developed by the Catalan cluster is a citizen science project to help improve the selective collection of municipal waste.

In Mollet del Vallès, the percentage of selective collection in 2020 was 39% (far from the 55% required by Europe for 2025 and the progressive increase required for the following years). To increase this percentage, the City Council is considering the implementation of innovative selective collection systems (smart bins and optional door-to-door collection), but it does not want to do this without first knowing the preferences of the citizens.

There is little information in Mollet on these preferences (which will vary according to the type of people, the urban structure, etc.), or on the variables that citizens take into account when adopting or rejecting innovations and the reasons for resistance to change. On the other hand, citizens need to be informed beforehand and have time to reflect on the pros and cons of these systems in order to be able to make an informed decision.

5.2.1 Objectives & specific impacts

In order to address this issue, the following objectives were collectively defined for the waste pilot:

- To **increase the public's knowledge** of innovative waste collection systems, opening up public debate.
- To generate active awareness of the environmental impact of waste, contributing to co-responsibility.
- To **collect citizens' assessments of and preferences** for innovative selective collection systems, to identify barriers and needs in the implementation of new waste collection systems.

To achieve these objectives, a pilot project was defined consisting of two activities: 1) the **co-design of a digital game on waste**, called "Dilemma R", together with citizens and students from the Autonomous University of Barcelona and 2) the **use of the game as a tool within a**

citizen science programme, involving secondary school students from Mollet del Vallès.

5.2.2 Organisations involved

The pilot has benefited from the participation of several actors (in addition to the Catalan cluster partners) with varying degrees of involvement.

Figure 2. Stakeholders involved in the waste pilot

- a) **Steering group:** is responsible for developing and monitoring all phases of the project and comprising the member organisations of the Catalan Cluster (Science for Change, OpenSystemsUB, Catalan Government) and the Mollet del Vallès City Council (member of the Think Tank). Meetings every two weeks.

Science for Change. In the pilot, together with OpenSystemsUB, it jointly leads the co-design process of each step of the pilot and its implementation. Together with Mollet del Vallès City Council and OpenSystemsUB, it leads the design and implementation of the strategy for citizen involvement. With OpenSystemsUB, it investigates social adoption with the aim of

promoting social change in relation to waste management. Together with OpenSystemsUB and the Catalan Government, it co-leads the assessment of the research process. Together with OpenSystemsUB, it co-leads the project's advocacy actions to promote the design of new waste management policies, incorporating citizen participation.

OpenSystemsUB. With Science for Change, it jointly leads the co-design process for each step of the pilot and its implementation. It jointly leads, together with Mollet del Vallès City Council and Science for Change, the design and implementation of the strategy for citizen involvement. Together with Science for Change, it investigates social adoption with the aim of promoting social change in relation to waste management. Together with Science for Change and the Generalitat de Catalunya, it co-leads the assessment of the research process. Together with Science for Change, it co-leads the project's advocacy actions to promote the design of new waste management policies, incorporating citizen participation.

*The **Catalan Government*** (through the Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds). In the project it is responsible for integrating the learnings of the project into RIS3CAT and for promoting the integration of Citizen Science into public policies. It explores how citizen science can contribute to more effective policies and actions and to a better understanding and management of the transition towards more sustainable development paths. It explores how citizen science can contribute to harnessing new forms of collaboration between academia, public administrations, business and civil society, to more effectively address the challenges that matter to society. Together with Science for Change and OpenSystemsUB, it co-leads the assessment of the research process.

Mollet del Vallès City Council is the administrative body in the area in which the pilot activities take place and was a member of the Think Tank. It is part of the Territorial Specialization and Competitiveness Project (PECT) "**HubB30, Beyond circularity**" which is a Zero Waste pilot scheme that should make it possible to design the method, optimal structure, and spaces for implementing a new model of interaction between the different Quadruple Helix agents and open innovation processes. To this end, the "HubB30, beyond circularity" project will bring together a network of "labs" in the region (OpenLabs), which will constitute the matrix in which the transformation towards a sustainable ecosystem of research and innovation begins.

A number of departments of the city council of Mollet del Vallès (participation, environment, education, communication and economic promotion) are actively involved. In addition to participating in the co-design process of each step of the pilot and its implementation, together with Science for Change and OpensystemsUB, it co-leads the design and implementation of the citizen engagement strategy. It is responsible for incorporating both the lessons learned from the process and its own results into future selective collection system plans in the municipality.

- b) **Collaborating agents:** the pilot has also benefited from the involvement of other agents who have contributed their knowledge and resources at different stages of its development:

The [***Autonomous University of Barcelona \(UAB\)***](#) is also a part of the Think Tank and the '[***HubB30, Beyond Circularity***](#)' project. It participates through a Challenge-Based Learning approach, using citizen science as a teaching tool. Its students on the Smart and Sustainable Cities Management Degree contribute by supporting various phases of the project through curricular placements and other teaching activities. The results of this collaboration are articles and Final Degree Projects that contribute to the documentation, analysis and evaluation of both the process and the results in the framework of the social adoption of environmental conduct and citizen science as a tool for improving public policies. Furthermore, students have been actively involved as facilitators of the participatory activities carried out throughout the pilot scheme.

- c) **Citizenship:** the citizens of Mollet del Vallès participated at several key moments:

- A group of 10-15 people were involved in the game co-design sessions.
- Later, 60 secondary school students from 4 schools in Mollet (Escola Sant Gervasi, Institut Vicenç Plantada, Escola Anselm Clavé, and Centre d'Estudis Mollet) took part in the game implementation phase, by getting the local residents involved, and in the data interpretation phase and formulation of recommendations.
- Finally, 402 people played the street game and rated the different aspects dealt with in the game.

5.2.3 Phases

5.2.3.1 Phase 1: Setting the challenge (June-December 2020)

Mollet del Vallès City Council set the challenge of improving the percentage of selective waste collection in the municipality, in the context of the Think Tank. The city council expressed its willingness to experiment with citizen science as a tool for incorporating citizens and their assessments into the public policy formulation cycle, in this case, on waste management.

5.2.3.2 Phase 2: Co-design of the digital waste game "Dilemma R" (March 2021-February 2022)

First, together with various City Council departments, the set of preferences and potential barriers associated with adopting the new collection systems were identified. Second, the most important phase, this identification was validated and enriched by a small group of citizens and, together with students from the Autonomous University of Barcelona, progress was made in the co-definition of the digital game and the associated experimental methods. The aim of this process was to detect the most pertinent variables for the different agents involved and to co-define the messages and hypothetical situations to be included in the game. In total, four sessions were held: two with citizens of Mollet with different profiles (10-15 people), one with various departments of the city council, and the fourth with students on the Management of Smart and Sustainable Cities Degree at the Autonomous University of Barcelona. This was followed by further digital development of the game made by an external company (see details in Annex 1).

Pictures 2 and 3. Pictures of the game Dilemma R

5.2.3.3 Phase 3: Use of the game as a tool within a citizen science programme (March-May 2022)

Once the game had been developed, a citizen science programme was rolled out involving 60 secondary school students from 4 schools in Mollet del Vallès (Escola Sant Gervasi, Institut Vicenç Plantada, Escola Anselm Clavé, and Centre d'Estudis Mollet). Over the course of four sessions, the students were able to increase their knowledge on waste management and statistics (see Annex 2), help define the data collection protocol, participate in the actual data collection (both in the street and with their families), interpret the results and draw up proposals for the City Council. The mayor, the first deputy mayor and technicians from the city council attended the last session to hear the students' recommendations first hand.

Pictures 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. Pictures of the students participating in the different phases of the citizen science program

5.2.3.4 Phase 4: Impact on public policies (June-September 2022).

The final phase involved the delivery of a results report (including recommendations) and a presentation of the results to the city council. This provided a clearer picture of the public's preferences regarding innovative selective waste collection systems, possible barriers to implementation, and other key aspects to consider when implementing these systems. The concrete impacts are reported on chapter 6. Another product generated was a brief summary of the results and recommendations, to be circulated among the students as a return.

Pictures 10 and 11. Images of the results report and the brief summary of the waste pilot

5.2.4 How has citizen science been applied in this pilot

What follows is an explanation of how the 10 Principles of citizen science have been implemented in this research:

Principles	Application
1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding.	The students have actively participated in a research project that has generated new scientific knowledge about the variables that citizens take into account when adopting or rejecting innovative selective waste collection systems and the reasons for resistance to change. The research used quantitative methods combined with the active participation component of citizen science (participatory and co-creation methods).
2. Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome.	
6. Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for.	
4. Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process.	Specifically, the students have actively participated in three phases of scientific research: a) design of the data collection protocol, b) data collection, by playing the game with their families and neighbours; and c) the results interpretation phase and the drafting of recommendations.

<p>5. Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.</p>	<p>At the beginning of the pilot, students' tutors signed an "Informed Consent" form in which they were informed of the objectives of the research and how their data and contributions would be used; they also received feedback about the final results as a return (in an informative and easy-to-read format).</p>
<p>9. Citizen science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.</p>	<p>The knowledge generated will be published in a scientific article and is being disseminated in other types of scientific (congresses) and educational communications.</p>
<p>3. Both professional and citizen scientists benefit from this participation.</p>	<p>The benefits perceived by the students and the social impact of the project have been evaluated by means of a final questionnaire and have been assessed as a project success criterion; the students have identified benefits with regard to increased scientific and waste management know-how, knowledge of other students in the region, and awareness of the various key players in the municipality (political decision-makers in the city council). In terms of political impact, the results have contributed to the definition of the city's new waste collection contract.</p>
<p>8. Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.</p>	<p>The participation of the students is acknowledged in all the documents and reports. They will also appear as co-authors, if they wish, in future scientific communications.</p>
<p>7. Citizen science project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open access format.</p>	<p>The data and metadata will be published on the ZENODO platform in open access format.</p>
<p>10. The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities.</p>	<p>The pilot has been validated by the University of Barcelona Bioethics Committee. It also complies with the GDPR standards regarding data protection. The activities have been designed trying to reduce the environmental impact as much as possible.</p>

Table 2. Application of the 10 principles of Citizen Science in the waste pilot

5.2.5 Levels of engagement in the pilot

As explained in the chapter above, the citizen scientists in this pilot are the 60 secondary students of Mollet del Vallès that have actively participated. The phases of scientific research in which they have participated are:

- **Design of the data collection protocol:** by defining, based on their knowledge of their local knowledge, the points in the city where they should be placed in order to reach the greatest number and diversity of Mollet's citizens.
- **Data collection:** by playing the game with their families and neighbors

- **Results interpretation:** participating in the reading of dynamic graphs and drawing results and conclusions from them.
- **Drafting of recommendations:** producing their own proposals on the basis of the results obtained and presenting them to the political decision-makers of the city council.
- **Extra task:** one student also participated in dissemination tasks, being invited to represent the student body in the local final event in Barcelona.

Taking into account the levels of engagement explained in chapter 3.3, this pilot should be considered **“Level 4: Extreme citizen science”**.

In addition, 402 citizens of Mollet actively participated in the project, although their participation was smaller and applicable only to data collection.

The Autonomous University of Barcelona (and its students) is also another stakeholder to be taken into account, who actively participated in the pilot by supporting various phases of the project through curricular placements and other teaching activities. The results of this collaboration are articles and Final Degree Projects that contribute to the documentation, analysis and evaluation of both the process and the results in the framework of the social adoption of environmental conduct and citizen science as a tool for improving public policies. Furthermore, students have been actively involved as facilitators of the participatory activities carried out throughout the pilot scheme.

The last but not least stakeholder involved is Mollet del Vallès City Council itself (different technical departments and political decision-makers), which participated in the co-design and monitoring of the whole process (meetings every 15 days) and in the commitment to evaluate the recommendations arising from the project as an additional input to be taken into account (in other areas such as technical and economic aspects, etc.) and to incorporate those they considered appropriate.

5.3 Pilot 2: Endometriosis in the first person: participatory research on experiences and recommendations of women with endometriosis for the improvement of health services

"We thought of the TRANSFORM project as a driving force for a change in the way we professionals see endometriosis. As professionals we only see the tip of the iceberg of a situation that many women suffer, but we are not clear about the implication that this has for the families and the women themselves. We thought that it was a project that had to be approached from a social point of view, from the patient's point of view, and that citizen science could help us to better understand the disease and to better help our patients".

Dr. Elisa Llurba. Director of the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service of the Hospital de la Sant Creu i Sant Pau.

The other pilot project of the Catalan cluster is a citizen science project on women's health called "Endometriosis in the first person: participatory research on experiences and recommendations of women¹⁴ with endometriosis for the improvement of health services", which aims to improve diagnostic and care services for endometriosis.

Endometriosis is an infradiagnosed disease affecting women's health (and other trans identities susceptible to endometriosis), in which the endometrium grows outside the uterine cavity. It can cause severe menstrual pain, painful intercourse, chronic pain, fertility problems and psychological disorders - depression, anxiety¹⁵. The drama comes with the statistics: Endometriosis affects 10-20% women of reproductive age globally¹⁶ and its diagnosis takes 8-10 years from the onset of symptoms¹⁷ - times during which women suffer severe physical,

¹⁴ In this research, we take an inclusive look at the different identities of people who are likely to be affected by endometriosis (women and other sex-gender identities). We will refer to people, women, co-investigators, participants and patients throughout the writing of this report. The term "women's health" refers to the need to adhere to a "medicine of difference" (Valls, C. 2020) that takes into account the specificities of women (including other sex-gender identities) and that is not yet present in current medicine.

¹⁵ Della Corte L, Di Filippo C, Gabrielli O, Reppuccia S, La Rosa VL, Ragusa R, Fichera M, Commodari E, Bifulco G, Giampaolino P. The Burden of Endometriosis on Women's Lifespan: A Narrative Overview on Quality of Life and Psychosocial Wellbeing. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020 Jun 29; 17 (13): 4683. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/17/13/4683>

¹⁶ Endometriosis, World Health Organisation. March 2021. <https://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/endometriosis>

¹⁷ Agarwal SK, Chapron C, Giudice LC, Laufer MR, Leyland N, Missmer SA, Singh SS, Taylor HS. Clinical diagnosis of endometriosis: a call to action. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2019 Apr; 220(4): 354.e1-354.e12. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30625295/>

psychological, social and professional consequences. Endometriosis is surrounded by gender issues and social norms that have led to the creation of myths and misbeliefs - affecting health services and necessary political support. Ignorance of the disease at both social and health care levels and underestimation of the pain expressed by women have contributed to a long delay in diagnosing endometriosis, poor research and insufficient health care. The project aims to increase knowledge of women's involvement in endometriosis and their experiences of health care in order to contribute to improving the clinical management of the disease.

For decades there has been a gender bias in medical research, in the diagnosis of diseases, and in their treatment¹⁸. We start from an androcentric medicine that has researched manifestations in men and extrapolated the results to women. Because of this bias, there are diseases that have been completely silenced and made invisible, and endometriosis is a clear example of this. There is little research and little scientific knowledge about the experience of endometriosis and about the biopsychosocial variables on which it affects, which is necessary, among other things, to make a clinical approach that covers all these spheres.

5.3.1 Objectives

In order to address this issue, the following objectives were collectively defined for the women's health pilot:

- **Creation of a group(s) of people with endometriosis** who talk in first person about their experience of the disease from the first symptoms to diagnosis and assess health care and support resources.
- **Co-creation of recommendations** for policy makers and health professionals to improve services and resources for endometriosis diagnosis and health care.

5.3.2 Organisations involved

The pilot has benefited from the collaboration of various agents throughout its development.

¹⁸ Valls, Carme. (2020). Mujeres invisibles para la medicina. Capitán Swing.

Figure 3. Organisations involved in the health pilot

- a. **Steering group:** responsible for developing and monitoring all phases of the project and comprising the member organisations of the Catalan Cluster (Science for Change, OpenSystemsUB, Catalan Government), the Sant Pau Hospital and The Catalan Health Quality and Assessment Agency (AQuAS). Meetings every two weeks.

Science for Change, in the pilot, co-leads the process of codesign of each step of the pilot and its implementation together with OpenSystemsUB and acts as a facilitator of the whole process. It co-leads, together with the Hospital de Sant Pau and Opensystems UB, the citizen involvement strategy. It investigates the key social dimensions to contribute positively to the public visibility of endometriosis, promote early diagnosis and improve the quality of life of people with endometriosis. It co-leads the evaluation of the research process together with OpenSystems UB and the Generalitat de Catalunya. It promotes new policies in relation to healthcare provision, together with OpenSystems UB and the Generalitat de Catalunya. It carries out actions to promote and disseminate the pilot.

OpenSystems UB, collaborates with Science for Change in the co-design process of each step of the pilot and its implementation. Co-leads, together with the Hospital de Sant Pau and Science for Change, the strategy of citizen involvement. It co-leads the evaluation of the research process together with Science for Change and the Catalan Government. It promotes new policies in relation to healthcare provision, together with Science for Change and the Catalan Government. It participates in the pilot's promotion and dissemination actions.

The **Catalan Government** (through the Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds). In the project it is responsible for integrating the learnings of the project into RIS3CAT and for promoting the integration of Citizen Science into public policies. It explores how citizen science can contribute to more effective policies and actions and to a better understanding and management of the transition towards more sustainable development paths. It explores how citizen science can contribute to harnessing new forms of collaboration between academia, public administrations, business and civil society, to more effectively address the challenges that matter to society. Together with Science for Change and OpenSystemsUB, it co-leads the assessment of the research process.

The **Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau**. Participates in the co-design and monitoring of all phases of the research. It co-leads the design and implementation of the citizen engagement strategy. It investigates key social dimensions to positively contribute to the public visibility of endometriosis, promote early diagnosis and improve the well-being of people with endometriosis. It promotes new internal policies in relation to healthcare provision and also the inclusion of research results in other public policies. It carries out actions to promote and disseminate the pilot.

The **Health Quality and Assessment Agency of Catalonia (AQuAS)**. Explores how citizen science can contribute to articulating new forms of collaboration between academia, public administrations, business and civil society to contribute to evidence-based policy making, including innovative forms of citizen participation. It contributes how to transfer and deliver the results to policy makers and other stakeholders within the system. It aims to promote new policies in relation to health care delivery.

- b. **Citizenship:** the women co-researchers have participated in various key moments of the research:

- In the data collection phase, participating in the focus groups and the participatory activities proposed to collect the information.
- In the formulation of recommendations, which they themselves drew up and corrected.
- In disseminating the results, sharing information through their social networks and participating in colloquiums.

5.3.3 Phases

5.3.3.1 Phase 1: Setting the challenge (June-December 2020)

Within the health group in the Think Tank, The Hospital de Sant Pau raised the challenge of "invisibility, under-diagnosis and lack of research into diseases specific to women: the case of endometriosis". At the root of this challenge, a first proposal of research objectives, data to be collected and participation strategies was made. Subsequently, outside of the TRANSFORM webinars, the steering group was created (composed of the Catalan cluster, Hospital de Sant Pau and AQUAS) with which the objectives and phases of the research were definitively defined.

5.3.3.2 Phase 2: Creation of the women's group to deepen understanding of key issues and identify needs regarding health services (April-June 2021):

During these months, a group of 20 women diagnosed with endometriosis was created, divided into 3 subgroups (online, face-to-face and by form). During 3 sessions, through social research techniques and participatory techniques, information was collected on the experiences of the disease, the biopsychosocial variables of affect and the perceived needs regarding health services.

Pictures 12 and 13. Illustrations that reflect the first sessions of the group

5.3.3.3 Phase 3: Co-creation of recommendations (July 2021 - April 2022)

During 2 sessions, the co-researchers defined and prioritised their recommendations for the improvement of diagnostic and healthcare services. This exercise resulted in 28 recommendations, grouped into 6 general recommendations.

Picture 14. illustration that reflect the co-creation sessions of the group

5.3.3.4 Phase 4: Impact on local public policies (April-December 2022):

The final phase involved the delivery of a results report (including the recommendations in first-person) to Hospital Sant Pau and AQUAS. This provided a clearer picture of the experiences of the disease and the experiences and needs of the women regarding health care services. A joint meeting between women and the professionals of Hospital San Pau was held (Nov, 19) to collectively comment on the results. Another product delivered was a policy brief, devoted to health professionals and policy makers. The impacts of these documents are reported in chapter 6.

Pictures 15 and 16: Images of the results reports and the policy brief of the women’s health pilot

5.3.4 How has citizen science been applied in this pilot

How the 10 Principles have been implemented in this research is explained below:

Principles	Application
1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding.	Women have actively participated in a research that has generated new scientific knowledge about the experiences of living with endometriosis, its effects on different biopsychosocial areas of life and the

<p>2. <i>Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome</i></p>	<p>needs in terms of the clinical approach from health services. The research has used qualitative research methods combined with the active participation component of citizen science (participatory and co-creation methodologies).</p>
<p>6. <i>Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for.</i></p>	
<p>4. <i>Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process.</i></p>	<p>Specifically, women have actively participated in three phases of the scientific research: a) data collection, participating in the focus groups and the proposed participatory and co-creation dynamics; b) drafting of recommendations, which were written in full and corrected by themselves; c) dissemination of the results, participating in workshops and round tables and/or sharing information in their social networks.</p>
<p>5. <i>Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.</i></p>	<p>At the beginning of the pilot, participants signed an "Informed Consent" in which they were informed of the objectives of the research and how their data and contributions would be used. In addition, participants are regularly informed of the progress of the pilot and its results through email updates and presentations of preliminary results. They have also been provided with a final return of results.</p>
<p>9. <i>Citizen science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.</i></p>	<p>The knowledge generated will be published in a scientific article and is being disseminated in other types of scientific communications (congresses) and dissemination actions.</p> <p>Women were asked at the beginning of the pilot about their expectations and the results were taken into account in research design and decision-making. The benefits perceived by the women participants and the social impact of the pilot will be evaluated by means of a final questionnaire and will be taken into account as a criterion for the success of the pilot. Benefits are expected in terms of increased knowledge about the scientific process, the management of endometriosis at health and public policy level, a sense of empowerment, links with the community and therapeutic benefits.</p>
<p>3. <i>Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part.</i></p>	
<p>8. <i>Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications</i></p>	<p>The participation of women is acknowledged in all papers and communications with the status of co-researchers. They will also appear as co-authors, if they wish so, in future scientific communications.</p>
<p>7. <i>Citizen science project data and metadata are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open-access format.</i></p>	<p>The data and metadata will be published on the ZENODO platform in open access format.</p>

10. The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data-sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution and the environmental impact of any activities.

The pilot has been validated by the [University of Barcelona Bioethics Committee](#). Furthermore, it complies with GDPR standards in terms of data protection. The activities have been designed with a view to minimising environmental impact.

Table 3. Application of the 10 principles of Citizen Science in the health pilot.

5.3.5 Levels of engagement in the pilot

As explained in the chapter above, the citizen scientists in this pilot are the **20 women diagnosed with endometriosis** that have actively participated. The phases of scientific research in which they have participated are:

- **Data collection:** participating in the focus groups and the proposed participatory and co-creation dynamics.
- **Drafting of recommendations:** producing their own proposals on the basis of the results obtained.
- **Dissemination of the results:** participating in workshops and round tables (including the participation of two of them as representatives for the group, during the final local event) and/or sharing information in their social networks.
- **Advocacy efforts:** two of women have (and are) also participated in the meetings with different policy makers in order to help ensure that research has an impact on the regional health system.

Taking into account the levels of citizen engagement explained in chapter 3.3, this pilot should be considered **“Level 4: Extreme citizen science”**.

The other relevant stakeholder involved is **Hospital de Sant Pau** itself, which participated in the co-design and monitoring of the whole process (meetings every 15 days) and in the commitment to evaluate the recommendations arising from the project and incorporate them to a new comprehensive endometriosis management model.

6. Impact in the region

As explained above, the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM aims at generating a number of short-term impacts through its activities, i.e. within the development of TRANSFORM. Those are both at local and regional levels.

Although at this moment it is not possible to determine the impact of TRANSFORM's activities in the long term (nor is the monitoring of this impact considered a task within the project), it is also possible to envision expected impacts beyond the project (long term) and it is also possible to explain the actions that the Catalan cluster is carrying out to that end.

6.1 Short term impacts - within TRANSFORM

Within this section, we provide information regarding the short term impacts of the Catalan cluster activities (Think Tank and the 2 citizen science pilots on waste and women's health). The impacts explained are both at local and regional level.

6.1.1 Local impact

Both the citizen science pilots and the Think Tank have generated the expected local impacts in public policies, which were:

- that the **process carried out in the citizen science pilots fosters the transformation of the local policy-making cycle** towards more responsible approaches, integrating the voice of citizens and other territorial actors (subsection 6.1.1.1)
- that the **results of the citizen science pilots are taken into account** for the development of future policies that are more aligned with social needs (subsection 6.1.1.2).

6.1.1.1 Fostering the transformation of the local policy-making cycle towards more responsible approaches, integrating the voice of citizens and other territorial actors.

With regard to the waste pilot, as expressed by the participating organisations, the development of the pilot has provided them with many lessons learned in the sense of

transforming a "top down" way of making public policies to a more responsible way, including the expertise of different agents, especially the voice of citizens, in the process.

From the point of view of Mollet del Vallès City Council, participation in the project has succeeded in generating dialogue and **bringing together different departments** that traditionally work separately. On the other hand, it has also allowed them to **incorporate the expertise of other external agents**, specially an important regional actor such as the University, generating a fruitful collaboration.

In the following paragraphs, some quotes from institutional actors are provided:

"The project allows us to work in a transversal way, both between the different departments within the city council (which is not the usual way), as well as with agencies from outside, so it helps us to align very different agents."

Albert del Amor. Former Programme Coordinator - Area of Open Government, Economic Development and Innovation, Mollet del Vallès city council

"It has been an experience that has allowed us to learn new work dynamics; especially working with the university, which you see has a different way of approaching a project like this. And then the breadth that we have been able to give to the project by working with different areas of knowledge, and being able to touch on all these issues. From the city council the technical level is more limited (regarding the different ways of focusing our approach) so the range has been greatly expanded."

Guifré Ortiz, Head of Urban Services Section

"This is always positive. Working hand in hand with the Autonomous University, with which we have many projects and is one of the most powerful universities in Spain. Also working with companies such as Science for Change, and with the other partners that have a lot of expertise in their field and they help us to improve. In the end, we as a council and as a city, are always open to improving and continuing to learn."

Raúl Broto, first deputy mayor and coordinator of the Area of Governance, territory and climate action of the Mollet del Vallès City Council

In addition, the pilot has allowed them to **incorporate the voice and action of the citizens**; on the one hand, of the students who have had the opportunity to issue their own recommendations and present them in front of the technicians and policy-makers of the city council; on the other hand, of the people who communicated their assessments and preferences through the waste game. A quote from an institutional actor is provided:

"It has given us the ability to create a work network. From the field of education we are used to doing transversal work with other municipal areas, but in this project it has been much broader; a link has been created with the university, with TRANSFORM... We also work a lot

with the students to get them to participate in city projects, to do participatory projects, like in the Children's Council, to try to make learning more meaningful, so that they contribute ideas to improve the city. The project has allowed that: that the students could contribute benefits and ideas on how to improve the city's waste management. In the end, the students are our future citizens and it is very good that we keep them in mind to make contributions for the improvement of the city and that we work with them to raise awareness."

Sandra Palma, manager of the Municipal Institute of Education of Mollet del Vallès

The teachers have also valued the experience positively, in the sense that their students have had the opportunity to link their learning process to the real challenges of the territory and to play an active role in the search for solutions. This is shown by the following quotes:

"For our students it has been a good learning experience participating in this service activity, doing research in a social field such as this."

"The fact that pupils can participate in the analysis and conclusions of situations occurring in their municipality."

Teachers of the secondary school groups that have taken part in the pilot project

From the point of view of the Autonomous University of Barcelona, the experience has also been highly positive because citizen science and the fact of working in a scheme that involves different actors in the territory, has **allowed university students to link their learning process to the real challenges of the territory**. A quote from the Autonomous University of Barcelona is provided:

"For us it has been an extraordinary opportunity to move from theory to practice. We have a long tradition of working with citizen science, but now we are in the process of integrating citizen science into the students' academic curriculum. And also to change the vision of how research should be, linking it to territorial challenges." "It has meant a very interesting opportunity to be able to apply the citizen science approach in our educational and formative context. The great interesting point, and it has been a really innovative activity within the university environment, has been to take on a challenge from the territory and involve students in this challenge, to be worked from citizen science. In this way, the students have been able to witness first-hand how the project has evolved, how they have been working together with the citizens on a territorial challenge. And they have collected all this knowledge, all this information that has been generated, to prepare their research papers and their publications in an academic environment. I believe that this communion between citizen science, public policies and the university, in this case, from the point of view of the students, has been an extraordinary step forward in their training, and a novel and very interesting experience for the university."

Xavier Ariño - Head of Institutional Projects - Rector's Office at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

In fact, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona is currently developing a Citizen Science HUB through the European [INCENTIVE](#) project, with the aim of increasing the role of the university in tackling challenges from the territory using citizen science. The UAB Hub is building upon existing citizen science initiatives and resources, which when coordinated, can facilitate the development of citizen science at the University to promote the contribution to societal challenges. The Hub aims to tackle societal challenges in the territory with the participation of the quadruple helix by developing new models of teaching, doing research, and promoting innovation.

With regards to the **pilot on women's health about endometriosis**, as expressed by the participating organisations, the development of the pilot has provided them with **many lessons learned for incorporating the voice of the patients in the process of improving healthcare services**.

In the following paragraphs, we provide some quotes of the participating institutions:

"As a service, participating in this project has allowed us firstly to go deeper into the disease as a team; we have discussed, we have had to think about it much more frequently and we have had to approach the subject from the patient's experience, within the hospital and with the connection also with primary care. This has allowed us to be better able to respond to women. Just by participating in this project, we have been able to rethink many circuits, many processes, which in the end help the patients."

Dr. Elisa Llurba. Director of the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service of the Hospital de la Sant Creu i Sant Pau.

"With the TRANSFORM project we have really put the patient at the centre. It has been an opportunity, as a professional, to know first-hand what patients need and a possibility of radical improvement to address changes in the therapeutic approach to this pathology at all levels"

Dr. Ramon Rovira, Surgical Coordinator, Oncology Coordinator and Endometriosis Unit Coordinator of the Gynaecology and Obstetrics Service of the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau.

“Citizen science has also opened our eyes to how we can work with the patients themselves, with the people who suffer from the disease. Finding new ways, because as doctors we have a more interventionist vision but on the other side we find things that you as a doctor do not see and that are important for the patient. Their satisfaction and peace of mind is fundamental for the success of the treatment. Involvement and feeling responsible for how it will be treated is very important. It is where we are going in the new models of care and approach.”

Caterina Sampol. Transformational change and value based procurement Manager at Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau.

It is also important to highlight the benefit that the women themselves have expressed regarding their participation in the TRANSFORM project. These benefits are expressed in the sense of therapeutic impacts, in the fact of having been able to share their experiences with other women in the same situation, and also in the sense that the results of the process can help to improve the situation at hospital level.

“Above all, it has allowed me to meet women who are in the same situation as me, to share our experiences, which has been very enriching, because together we have been able to build, from all our stories, a great story that can be used here at Sant Pau’s Hospital to make improvements and really meet our needs.”

Marta Fonseca, woman co-researcher in the pilot

“We are proving that this research process generates a double benefit: on the one hand, it contributes to an improvement of the health services and on the other hand, the project has a therapeutic effect for the patients, as they share their experiences with each other and find mutual support, new knowledge on the disease and a women’s network to be able to share their experiences.”

Nora Salas Seoane, Head of the Health Area. Science for Change

From all the participating institutions and pilot experiences, we can affirm that in both pilots, the voices of the citizens and other key territorial actors have been included to transform the local policy making cycle towards a more responsible approach which is aligned with societal needs and contributes to advance and innovate in societal challenges.

6.1.1.2 Results of the citizen science pilots taken into account for the development of future policies that are more aligned with social needs

In this subsection, we provide evidences on the results of both pilots to contribute to the development of future policies that are more aligned with societal needs.

In the case of the waste pilot, the establishment of the new selective waste collection and street cleaning contract has taken place within the timetable of the TRANSFORM project. For this reason, we can state today that **the results of the pilot have not only been taken into account but have actually been incorporated into the new waste collection contract**, as shown in the following extract from a [news](#) item published by the city council on 28 June:

“One of the proposals that has been evaluated and finally incorporated into the new set of clauses of the contract for the city's waste collection service is the result of the EU TRANSFORM citizen science pilot project, carried out by the City Council with the UB, the UAB, the Generalitat de Catalunya and 'Science for Change”.

“The interactive game has been used by students with their families and on the street with the aim of gathering enough information to process and analyse this information in the form of a survey to ensure that the results are statistically representative. From the analysis, the project concludes that smart bins are the preferred option for waste collection in the city of Mollet”.

The following quotes also show how the results of the pilot have provided relevant information on citizens' preferences.

“So far it's been a good start. It has reinforced a little of what we already thought and has given us guidelines for the future, to facilitate the implementation of new collection systems and with prior knowledge of what citizens think. These ideas will make it easier for us not to make all the mistakes that we could have committed but only a few. I think it's a way to start a new project with a much more solid foundation than we had until now.”

Guifré Ortiz, Head of Urban Services Section in Mollet del Vallès City Council

“It has mainly given us more information, knowing more about what our citizens think about such an important issue as waste management. In this project we have worked on two things. One is the educational and pedagogical issue with the students. They have also helped us spread this knowledge among their families and other citizens. Secondly, what we have worked on has had a real impact, and we have achieved it, with the new waste management specifications, which has incorporated knowledge that we had worked on in the project.”

Raúl Broto, first deputy mayor and coordinator of the Area of Governance, territory and climate action of the Mollet del Vallès City Council

In the case of the women's health pilot, the recommendations co-created by the co-researchers are being taken into account by the Hospital de Sant Pau in the process of

improving the approach and health services for care and support of patients with endometriosis from the Gynaecology Area.

In this sense, a joint meeting was held on 19th October between the Gynaecology professionals of Hospital de Sant Pau and the women co-researchers of the project, to collectively discuss the results of the pilot and the co-created recommendations to improve healthcare services. This meeting was attended by the Director of the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service; the Head of the Reproductive Medicine Department; the Surgical & Oncology Coordinator, also Endometriosis Unit Coordinator of the Gynaecology and Obstetrics Service; the Transformational change and value based procurement manager; the Innovation Project Manager; and from the Patient's Experience and Strategy Office, all part of the Hospital Sant Pau.

Picture 17. Women and professionals of Hospital Sant Pau in Barcelona in a joint meeting to discuss research results and recommendations to improve healthcare services.

During this joint meeting, the Hospital explained what changes were already underway in order to improve the clinical approach to endometriosis and the health care services, as well as the recommendations driving from the research that the hospital intends to work on in the future. However, the hospital also highlighted the difficulties they face in improving the quality of care and introducing changes in the approach to the disease, mainly due to lack of funding and increased assistential pressure at hospital level. This means that the changes that are already being made have had to be done on a voluntary basis by the professionals, and not because of institutional support.

In fact, the Hospital de Sant Pau is planning to implement, among others, one of the specific recommendations made by the women: “To create therapeutic support groups and patient councils to share experiences and to act as a support network” which is classified within the general recommendation 4) Define and implement a comprehensive endometriosis management model (see entire [policy brief](#) for all recommendations).

Picture 18. Image of recommendation number 4 of the pilot's policy brief

The aim is to introduce these therapeutic groups at a hospital level, first of all as a pilot, in order to make them sustainable throughout the care and attention of endometriosis. Psychological affections are at the core of this disease and these groups in other diseases have proven to improve the quality of life of patients at a psychological level and act as a patient's network to better cope with the disease. Besides, these groups can also have an economic impact in reducing assistencial pressure if the information shared by professionals attending the groups is enough to diminish the anxiety towards certain symptoms/situations.

Hospital de Sant Pau together with Science for Change presented the women's health pilot on endometriosis as an example of innovative approach taking into account the voices of the

affected women to improve healthcare services at the hospital level to the Awards [CSC Impulsa](#). CSC Impulsa is an initiative promoted by the Innovation and Partnership Area of the [Health and Social Consortium of Catalonia](#) (CSC), in collaboration with [Roche Farma](#), which seeks to promote innovation in the health system, encouraging the culture of innovation in organisations. We are now happy to announce that we have won the second award which has economic funding to continue with the project. The implementation of this recommendation will be possible thanks to the funding that the hospital will receive from this award and this will be done together with the company Science for Change.

In the image below, professionals from Science for Change and Hospital de Sant Pau taking the award won.

Picture 19. Image of the CSC Impulsa Awards Ceremony on 27 October 2022, Barcelona.

On the other hand, doctors participating in the health pilot are also part of the group that is revising the [“Model of care for endometriosis in Catalonia”](#) (GENCAT). The date by which this document will be revisited is unknown, but it can be expected that the results of the pilot will be taken into account on the new revised model thanks to all the experience and knowledge gained during the project in relation to the needs expressed by endometriosis

patients and the innovative approach accompanying it. If that were to happen, the impact would move from the local to the regional scale. The team is already holding meetings to walk towards this direction. For instance, the project has been presented to the Head of Reproductive Health at the Health Department of the Generalitat de Catalunya, the Regional Government of Catalonia.

“We have enthusiastic medical staff. Some of the people involved in the pilot are part of the group that is reviewing the model of care, and they have an approach to make major changes at the system level. They are willing to make internal changes to integrate the results of this project, beyond the model itself.”

Caterina Sampol. Transformational change and value based procurement manager at Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau

Also in the line of **scaling-up the results of the pilot towards a regional impact, in this case reaching out to the political level**, conversations are being held between the Catalan cluster and members of the [Health Commission](#) of the Parliament of Catalonia to present the research results and the recommendations made by women to improve healthcare services. A formal meeting will be held before the end of the year (it was already scheduled but postponed due to the internal changes which have happened within the Catalan Government last October 2022).

6.1.2 Regional impact

Both the citizen science pilots and the Think Tank have also generated the expected impacts at regional level, which were:

- that **RRI and citizen science are integrated in RIS3CAT 2030** and some of the funding programmes and strategies that are developed within this framework.
- that **Think Tank member organisations** (both those participating in the implementation of the pilots and those not) **increase their knowledge on RRI and citizen science** and learn first-hand about the practical benefits of applying citizen science in R&I projects.

In the following subsections, the regional impacts are properly explained.

6.1.2.1 *Integration of RRI and citizen science in the RIS3CAT 2030.*

Thanks to the contribution of TRANSFORM, RRI and citizen science are integrated in the [RIS3CAT 2030](#) and in the Knowledge Regions Programme. This Programme promotes that universities and research and technological centers work with the territory and for the territory (with a quadruple helix approach) to address global challenges in a more effective way.

In the last 4 years the Catalan Government, through the unit coordinating and monitoring Catalonia's Smart specialisation Strategy, has participated in TRANSFORM (2020-2022) and also in the SeeRRI project (2019-2021), both devoted to RRI. While TRANSFORM has focused on how to engage citizens into public policies to better address those challenges that really matter (mostly related to the SDGs) using citizen science methodological approaches and tools, SeeRRI focused on how to build more responsible research and innovation ecosystems. Both projects have had a direct impact on the RIS3CAT 2030 design.

RIS3CAT 2030 is firmly committed to transformative and responsible research and innovation and RRI and citizen science appear in the new RIS3CAT 2030 as specific approaches.

Unlike the RIS3CAT of the 2014-2020 period, the RIS3CAT 2030 does not prioritise areas of specialisation but promotes:

- A sustainable, fair, equitable and healthy food system.
- An energy and resource system that is neutral in emissions and respectful of the environment
- A sustainable mobility and logistics system
- A universal, sustainable and resilient social and health care system
- A **reflective, anticipatory, inclusive and responsive** education and knowledge generation system and responsive
- A sustainable and competitive industrial system
- A cultural system that is inclusive of people, territory and history

As can be seen, the four principles of RRI (inclusion, anticipation, reflection, and responsiveness) are included in the strategy. So is citizen science as a specific methodology to be promoted, as can be seen in these excerpts from the strategy.

“The RIS3CAT 2030 is committed to transformative and responsible research and innovation and shared agendas as the main drivers to guide Catalonia towards a greener, more digital, resilient and fairer, digital, resilient and fairer socio-economic model.”

“Within the framework of the RIS3CAT 2030, the Opportunities Discovery Mechanism and the Regions of Knowledge programme promote knowledge as a driver of territorial development. More specifically, they promote the development of the concept of citizen science, of science at the service of people and science made with people.”

In addition to the text of the RIS3CAT itself, specific funding programmes are derived from them that specify the approach described in practice.

In RIS3CAT, shared agendas are the main drivers guiding Catalonia towards a greener, more digital, more resilient and fairer socioeconomic model. The word “transformative” describes research and innovation that promote substantial changes in production and consumption systems and contribute to creating a new digital and technology-based industry. “Responsible” means that all stakeholders (researchers, citizenry, public administrations, companies and civil society associations) collaborate in research and innovation with the aim of aligning processes and results with the values, needs and expectations of society.

RIS3CAT 2030 takes as a frame the [National Pact for the Knowledge Society](#). This Pact says that innovation policies should address the diverse economic and social realities of the Catalan territories, which all have different singularities and opportunities. Accordingly, RIS3CAT 2030 promotes policies and instruments that enable the identification of challenges and opportunities in the territories and strengthen the role of the knowledge system to respond to them in collaboration with businesses and society. Universities and facilitation infrastructures (such as science and technology infrastructure or social innovation labs) should ensure that knowledge, technology and innovation become universal for all people, wherever they live. The Opportunities Discovery Mechanism and the knowledge regions Programme promote knowledge-based shared agendas as a driver of territorial development and transformative change. More specifically, they promote the development of the concept of citizen science – science at the service of people and science made with people. In this, they involve social and cultural agents in identifying the challenges of the territory and in proposing and designing research and innovation projects that respond to the problems that concern people.

The Think Tank discussions and the experiences of the pilot projects have had a direct impact on the introduction of citizen science in the RIS3CAT 2030. Generalitat de Catalunya with the other two partners of the Catalan Transform cluster, and other actors participating in the TRANSFORM Think Tank and in the pilot projects, are exploring options to continue and disseminate the work done, through capacity building to research and innovation organisations, public administrations, students and citizens in general. Through the Regions of Knowledge Programme, promoted by the regional Ministry of Research and Universities in the frame of the RIS3CAT 2030, Generalitat de Catalunya will support citizen science projects supporting more effective public policies and actions to address the SDGs and the related problems and opportunities. The RIS3CAT 2030 Innovation Public Procurement Programme also integrates citizen science to improve public services. The first edition includes a project focused on monitoring noise and mapping quiet areas in cities through Citizen Science.

We can also say that, as a result of the discussion in the Think Tank, the Catalan Government has promoted a [study on the R&I projects in Catalonia focused on women's health](#). For that it was necessary to define a controlled vocabulary with experts to define the concept of women's health, in which some of the Think Tank members have participated as experts.

6.1.2.2 Think Tank member organisations increase their knowledge on RRI and citizen science and learn first-hand about the practical benefits of applying citizen science in R&I projects.

Organisations that have not participated directly in the pilots but have participated in Think Tank have also benefited from this participation. Receiving capacity building, being able to participate in the design of the pilots together with other actors and following up on the pilots has increased both their knowledge and their skills to develop this perspective in the future. This is shown by the following statements from an evaluation questionnaire on the webinars:

What did you get out of participating in the TRANSFORM webinars?

- Theoretical framework of RRI and CC, applied knowledge of projects and motivation/reflection to apply CC mechanisms to future projects (as well as tools and methodologies to lead online work groups).

- Better understanding of concepts and processes, and practising collaborative methodology.
- The webinars have helped me to better understand the concept of citizen science, the different levels of participation and the techniques to promote it.
- The need to incorporate all possible actors in the quadruple helix when thinking about and preparing proposals that include citizen science.
- It has provided knowledge and ideas on how to incorporate citizen science and responsible research into the design of the call for research in democratic quality.
- Knowledge of cross-cutting aspects of citizen participation, with the aim of involving the maximum number of actors in any decision-making process, thus increasing future success.
- I was pleased to learn about the methodology for designing a citizen science project and to do so with a real challenge and a real challenge owner.
- A new practical vision of how to improve the incorporation of CC in my projects, that is, in projects promoted by the public administrations (also third sector) with which I work.
- I have been able to go deeper into the RRI dimensions and the levels of application of citizen science. Likewise, the work carried out in the health group has allowed me to learn in a collaborative way, a different way of working, and to develop projects from the ground up. It was very interesting because the views of all the sectors involved were present, and the problem addressed, being a very real problem, it was very easy to get involved with enthusiasm.

In fact, some of these organisations have, indeed, developed projects and strategies that include citizen science and RRI as a perspective. While it cannot be said that this process is exclusively due to their participation in TRANSFORM, it can be assumed that this participation has contributed positively by providing ideas, methodologies and tools.

For example, in 2021, the **Department of Territory and Sustainability** of the Catalan Government created the "**Commission for the Promotion of Citizen Science and Nature**", a group made up of 14 organisations including local authorities, research groups and environmental entities. The main objectives of the group are to coordinate citizen science and nature actions in Catalonia, creating synergies between the actors involved, and to boost citizen science and nature in Catalonia by agreeing on a framework for joint work, and developing promotion and consolidation actions.

Given that citizen science is currently one of the main sources for generating data on biodiversity, one of the first actions within this commission was to carry out a diagnosis of the situation of the sector and the preparation of a Manual of good practices to help consolidate citizen science and nature projects in Catalonia (commissioned to SfC). Within the future work plan, it is envisaged that the Department of Territory and Sustainability will continue to carry out actions to promote the sector (direct funding, training, etc.).

Another example is the "[EAPC research engine](#)" programme of the **Public Administration School of Catalonia**. While this programme has existed as a pilot since 2018, the EAPC has renewed the approach to grants for research projects on public administration and public policy, based on the principles of RRI, to include the collaborative research approach and to emphasise knowledge transfer between academia, public management and civil society. This new approach has been implemented in the 2021 call, where SfC was also invited as a trainer for the grant winners.

6.2 Long term impacts - beyond TRANSFORM

Some long-term impacts can be envisioned as a result of the citizen science pilots and the Think Tank activities. These expected long term impacts are:

- **Local impact:** that the organisations that have participated in the development of the citizen science pilots incorporate this methodology in the development of future projects aimed at tackling socio-environmental challenges through R&I.
- **Regional impact:** that the organisations participating in the Catalan Think Tank and others within the Catalan R&I ecosystem incorporate citizen science as a means of integrating RRI within its future R&I projects and strategies.

At the following subsections, local and regional impacts at long-term level are tackled.

6.2.1 Local impacts

6.2.1.1 Organisations participating in the citizen science pilots incorporate this methodology in the development of future R&I projects

Organisations that have participated in both pilots are showing a clear intention to continue using the citizen science methodology for future R&I projects linked to social and environmental challenges.

With regard to the **women's health pilot**, two long term impacts of TRANSFORM can be envisioned in that sense. On the one hand, as explained in 6.1.1.2, the Hospital de Sant Pau is planning to implement, among others, one of the specific recommendations made by the women, which is to create therapeutic groups to improve the quality of life of women at a psychological level. These groups, as well as being therapeutic, will have a citizen science approach, in order to continue working towards actively involving women in the process of improving healthcare services. They can also have an economic impact in terms of diminishing the visits to healthcare professionals.

On the other hand, the Hospital de Sant Pau has recently created a Patient's Experience and Strategy Office within the Citizens Innovation and User's Area with the aim of continuing to work on incorporating the voice of patients into the evaluation of health quality and the process of improving the healthcare services for various diseases. The pilot has served as an example to demonstrate the potential of citizen science as a tool for this process and its incorporation into future projects carried out in this area is being strongly considered.

"Nowadays it is compulsory to incorporate the patients' experience. In hospitals we don't have the tools, because we don't have the time or the technical capacity to get to know the needs and wishes of patients. Therefore, the fact that there are teams like those of citizen science, which give us the opportunity to enjoy it, is a unique opportunity. This needs to be increasingly incorporated at the healthcare level, not only for this disease but for many others, because in the end we are at the service of society and sometimes it seems that society is at our service, which is not the case. We need to be more aware of the needs of the population in order to provide a better response. In the end, the important thing is not what we want but what patients need and want."

Dr. Elisa Llurba. Director of the Obstetrics and Gynaecology Service of the Hospital de la Sant Creu i Sant Pau.

"The results of this initiative are "a clear example for new projects in different areas of health that allow a paradigm shift in patient care in general. Knowing what the patient needs is one of the obligations of medical care in the future."

Dr. Ramon Rovira, surgical coordinator of the Gynaecology and Obstetrics Service of the Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau

"The results of the pilot helped us to further understand how citizen science can be used to influence health public policies and identified what are the current barriers and facilitators. It also allowed us to collaborate with a very multidisciplinary team, composed by different stakeholders with very different missions and visions, which showed us new lines of work for including the patient perspective."

Dr. Esther Vizcaino, Researcher at the Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia.

With regard to the **waste pilot**, long-term impacts can also be envisioned in the sense of the integration of citizen science as a tool to face socio-environmental challenges through R&I in the future. Specifically, within the framework of the HUB B30 project, in 2023 the city council of Mollet is planning to develop a citizen science project to co-create innovative solutions with citizens to reduce the generation of plastics in the municipal market.

6.2.2 Regional impact

6.2.2.1 Organisations participating in the Catalan Think Tank and others within the R&I ecosystem incorporate citizen science as a means of integrating RRI within its future R&I projects and strategies.

With regards to **waste policies**, the challenge of Mollet's municipality is meaningful and relevant for all municipalities in Catalonia and Europe, since it is compulsory to achieve the ambitious objectives set by the European Commission for waste selection and recycling. In Catalonia in the last years many municipalities have tried to implement innovations in waste recollection systems. What in theory were good ideas in the practice have encountered enormous resistances from citizens. The pilot in Mollet has demonstrated how it is possible to engage citizens in public policies, taking into account needs, fears, preferences of different collectives and delivering services better aligned with real needs. To spread the word within the waste management sector is one of the objectives of the last and most important TRANSFORM dissemination activity, which is the final local event. Not only have the members

of the Think Tank been invited to this event (among which are various environmental managers from local public administrations) but a strategy is being developed to invite other actors with the same profile from all over the Catalan territory. One of the most important players in the sector is the Waste Agency, which is a member of the Think Tank. The Waste Agency, also in the framework of RIS3CAT (public procurement of innovation programme) has been working the past years on how to engage citizens in the reduction of waste. It is hoped that the learnings from the pilot and the participation in the Think Tank will help the Waste Agency to value citizen science as a useful tool in this endeavour, fostering the development of future calls with citizen science integrated.

With regards to health policies, the citizen health science pilot tackling women with endometriosis in the domain of women's health has had an impact regarding the use of innovative methodologies such as citizen science applied to the sector. For instance, the pilot is generating a lot of interest in the hospital sector at regional level, especially among those actors working for the integration of the patient perspective in the evaluation and improvement of health services. This is demonstrated, for example, by the fact that Science for Change was invited to present the research in a [clinical session on Patient Experience](#) devoted to health professionals, organised by one of the leading hospitals in the field (Hospital Clínic de Barcelona).

Picture 20. Image of the clinical session on Patient Experience organised by Hospital Clínic de Barcelona

Science for Change was also invited to present the pilot in the [X Barcelona Patient Congress 2022](#) and the project was selected amongst the [5 best projects meeting the patient's experience](#). Nora Salas Seoane, Head of the Health Area, presented the pilot at the first roundtable of the congress.

The pilot is also gaining interest at the European level, and this may provide opportunities to further develop citizen science in the field of endometriosis through new European calls. Evidence of this is the relationship that Science for change has established with the [European H2020 project FEMaLe](#), which is interested in getting to know more closer the methodologies used in the pilot and invited Science for Change to present them in a webinar within the project scope (check the [article created in this regard in the TRANSFORM website](#)). The webinar aimed to share with an audience of health professionals, researchers and patients the variety of methodologies in the citizen science domain which could be applied to endometriosis and other diseases.

Webinar

First-person experiences of endometriosis:
Participatory research about the experiences, needs and recommendations of people with endometriosis

Ulrik Bak Kirk Nora Salas Seoane Diana Reinoso

Science for Change TRANSFORM

Picture 21. Image of the webinar organised by FEMaLe-TRANSFORM.

Finally, a specific strategy for the health sector will also be designed with a view to holding the final local event. Other actors in the field of health (in addition to the participants in the Think Tank) with whom the Catalan cluster has a relationship will be invited to it.

7. Reflections on the potential of citizen science for shared agendas: learnings from the TRANSFORM project

“This project is providing us with increased knowledge about citizen science. We see citizen science as a complementary tool to traditional public consultations. We see that it is a much more powerful tool and can provide very valuable data, because it is more “granular”; it can also integrate opinions from people who are not normally involved in participatory processes.”

“It requires collaboration between public administration (they have the questions), citizens (they have the answers) and researchers (they are the intermediaries).”

Tatiana Fernández, Head of the Area of Economic Strategy of the Catalan Government

This section expresses the reflections made by the Area of Economic Strategy of the Catalan Government, after the experience of the TRANSFORM project, about the potential contribution of citizen science to addressing societal challenges in the framework of the shared agendas of the RIS3CAT 2030. These reflections will be published in a future article that will be part of the "[RIS3CAT Monitoring Collection](#)".

Within the framework of the RIS3CAT and the shared agendas, the TRANSFORM project focuses on the experimentation of the practice with a specific participatory methodology. The Catalan TRANSFORM cluster designs a methodology to implement a new model of interaction between administration and citizens, a new model of governance. Thus, as citizen science ensures that scientific projects are linked to social needs, it is a key element in the process of transforming territories towards more sustainable, inclusive, resilient and just patterns of development.

Citizen science can contribute both to mapping challenges and to developing and experimenting with possible solutions. Specifically, citizen science can contribute to co-defining the shared framework for understanding the challenges that concern society (social, environmental or economic challenges that affect certain groups or territories) and articulating the necessary collective action to address them.

The differential traits of the TRANSFORM project lie in the promotion of the co-production of knowledge. This means that Catalan cluster collaborate with other institutions and entities as well as with "scientific citizens" from the very beginning. In an exercise of collaborative radicalism, the citizens, the collaborators and the Catalan clusternot only work together to detect the challenges but they also co-disseminate the pilots that help to clarify the possible solutions.

Although citizen science generates collaborative progress and allows stakeholders to identify the challenge and define the causes of the problem, the most complex exercise is trust-building. The design of any solution involves reconciling different perspectives and interests, but often the actors are not flexible enough and tensions emerge between the channels of accountability. Although the facilitating team must be aware of this, citizen science makes it possible to combine perspectives and strategies when it comes not only to redefining the problem but also to designing solutions. Moreover, citizen science helps to identify the root of the problem and develop a collaborative response.

Based on the debates held in the framework of the project and the work with the shared agendas, we have identified three areas in which citizen science plays a key role. They are as follows:

- Articulation of collective action to move towards a more sustainable, resilient and just socio-economic model.
- Collection and integration of data from multiple sources to generate new knowledge relevant to understanding the challenges and addressing them effectively.
- Awareness-raising and empowerment of people for a more democratic society

The debates, reflections and learning generated have gone beyond the scope of the TRANSFORM project and have led to complementary initiatives and actions within the framework of the RIS3CAT 2030, as explained in section

8. Practical recommendations to co-design and implement transformative citizen science projects

The second generation of smart specialisation strategies (2021-2027) are oriented to address the challenges that matter to society in a responsible way, this is integrating the four dimensions of RRI: anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness.

In this context, Smart Specialisation Strategies face two main challenges:

- **The transformative challenge**, which is strong related to the question about how R&I contribute to more sustainable and inclusive development pathways
- **The stakeholders engagement challenge**, which can be reformulated as the challenge of moving from collective awareness about societal challenges (like climate change) towards collective action to address these challenges.

The **TRANSFORM project has provided spaces for experimentation** and debate with quadruple stakeholders about how to integrate RRI into S3 and policies in general. The project has focused on citizen science as a tool for co-designing public policies that are more effective in addressing the challenges that matter to society, engaging citizens in policy-making and public services co-design and monitoring processes.

The development of the activities of the Catalan cluster over the three years of the **project has been highly successful in achieving its main objective, which was to foster the incorporation of participatory strategies and citizen science in the RIS3CAT**, its instruments, and the "business as usual" of the organisations within the R&I ecosystem.

This process, however, like all processes that require profound changes in the way of working and in the mindset of the people and organisations involved, **has not been without challenges that have had to be overcome** throughout the project in order to achieve the expected result. As a fruit of this learning process, we can now express what have been the main challenges encountered by the Catalan cluster and the collaborating organisations, as

well as practical recommendations to overcome them. These challenges and recommendations correspond to **two different levels (which are the levels that have been used in the project and should not be confused)**:

- the process of **multi-stakeholder engagement and coordination**, through the incorporation of various agents (in this case academia, regional and local public administration, and citizens). The incorporation of these various agents is what guarantees that the process and results of citizen science projects have an impact on public policies.
- the **citizen science process itself**.

“We have encountered many difficulties but now I see them more as opportunities. We all came with different interests and objectives, but we have been able to manage the different expectations: finding the area of shared interest (beyond the particular objectives) is the most important thing. We have been very flexible, very clear and very direct about this, and in the end we have found it. When you don't have the route defined from the beginning it can be more flexible.”

Tatiana Fernández, Head of the Area of Economic Strategy of the Catalan Government

At this point in TRANSFORM, we can **state some basic guidelines** to be taken into account for those who would like to co-design transformative citizen science projects based on the learnings from the Catalan cluster.

8.1 Preparing the ground: the creation of a Think Tank to learn, reflect on and work for transformative innovation

The creation of a Think Tank with actors from the triple helix, all involved in the territorial research and innovation ecosystem, has been a first step that has been necessary for the project itself. This action was led by The Secretariat for Economic Affairs and European Funds (SEAEF) as the regional authority. The Think Tank was composed of policy makers from the regional government, policy makers from local administrations, researchers from universities and research centres and companies and entities providing public services. Moreover, civil associations related to specific challenges would have been of great value to be added.

8.1.1 Challenge 1: engaging the actors

Creating a Think Tank to work collectively to make R&I more accountable involves identifying and involving the most relevant actors in the ecosystem. This task is difficult considering that this objective is not necessarily shared by many institutions that may be more interested in continuing to work in the traditional way. Currently, the European Commission and other institutions are specifically promoting this perspective (for example, by making citizen participation a requirement in Horizon Europe projects), but we must accept the reality that in many ecosystem actors there are inertias and resistance to change that hinder this process.

Practical recommendations:

In TRANSFORM it has been crucial that the institution that has led the creation of the Think Tank has been the Catalan Government, specifically the department in charge of the coordination and the monitoring of Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy. This type of institution has the necessary knowledge of the ecosystem and the actors that make it up, and therefore has the capacity to identify and locate the relevant actors in the ecosystem who might be most interested in or willing to work with this perspective.

It is also important, when approaching stakeholders, to have a very clear idea of what is to be achieved and what the benefits for the stakeholders could be, taking into account their particular needs and challenges. To ensure this, the TRANSFORM project carried out a good practice that can be replicated: this was to carry out surveys before and after each session, to detect what the needs and expectations of the stakeholders were and to be able to adapt the programme accordingly. Another good practice is to write feedback documents for the participants, summarising the results of each session.

This engagement process can also mean that actors who do not show an interest in participating in this transformative process or who do not perceive its benefits have to be "let go". The members of the Think Tank can be considered as the vanguard that, thanks to their commitment and their actions, will serve as an example to gradually spread the word to the rest of the ecosystem, hoping that in the coming years more and more institutions will join the process.

8.1.2 Challenge 2: incorporating citizen science in RIS3CAT ongoing projects

The original idea expressed in the Grant Agreement was to embed Innovative Citizen Science and its participatory strategies in at least three ongoing RIS3CAT projects (meaning to

replicate the same methodologies in the three ongoing projects, expected to be in the framework of the Public Procurement of Innovation call of the Catalan Waste Agency and/or the Utilities 4.0 RIS3CAT community).

Conversations were held with different agents of the R&I ecosystem linked with this Ris3CAT ongoing projects to gauge their interest in participating in TRANSFORM; then the difficulty of introducing the participatory element in existing and ongoing projects became clear: Utilities 4.0 RIS3CAT community were too advanced in their development to be open to introducing new elements in their planning; in fact, some of them were partially or totally inactive at that time. For its part, the Catalan Waste Agency's call for Public Procurement of Innovation was being delayed in its resolution so it was not possible to finally know the specific beneficiaries of this call. Therefore, it was considered that the cascade funding mechanism was not adequate to guarantee the objectives and the impact expected for the project and that the ideal mechanism was for the pilot proposals to emerge directly from the participatory exercises carried out by the Think Tank (always maintaining the selection criteria previously defined by the Catalan cluster, see Milestone 8).

Practical recommendations:

It is preferable to create citizen science projects from scratch with agents who have previously shown interest in carrying out transformative change processes. In this way it is guaranteed 1) that citizen science aspects are integrated into the design of the project itself; 2) that the organizations that are part of it are truly committed or at least encouraged to experiment with a new way of doing things. Ongoing R&I projects have already created structures and a rigidity in the design that makes it difficult to introduce changes or a change in the midst.

8.1.3 Challenge 3: increasing knowledge and skills to promote a change in the mindset

RRI is a complex concept and so is its practical application. Many actors in the R&I ecosystem may be interested in integrating this perspective into their projects, strategies and the internal working of their institutions, but do not necessarily have the knowledge and skills to do so.

Practical recommendations:

There is a need to create spaces to offer training to actors, to generate debate and also to experiment with methodologies to develop this perspective. Providing capacity building to the actors is crucial to foster a mindset change. In this sense, the use of digital media (webinar videoconferences) greatly facilitates the possibility that actors from different parts of the region can attend these training sessions.

8.1.4 Challenge 4: defining real challenges collectively

Another risk of this process is to get stuck in theoretical and abstract reflection, and not mobilise efforts towards action. In fact, some comments collected in the evaluation surveys of the webinars went in this direction: there are many formations and spaces for debate but normally these initiatives remain motivational but do not help or facilitate the actors to take action.

Practical recommendations:

To avoid this it has been very useful to include participatory strategies in these capacity building programs which has also helped the actors to directly experiment with methodologies to develop a common vision, to identify real challenges to be faced and to co-design projects to tackle these challenges, with a view to collective action. It is important to encourage stakeholders to be proactive and take the initiative in the codesigned projects.

8.2 Jumping into action: Setting up the steering group to develop the citizen science project

Another success factor of the Catalan cluster has been the creation of steering groups (composed of various stakeholders who were members of the Think Tank) to work collaboratively in the citizen science pilots.

8.2.1 Challenge 5: engaging the relevant organisations

A collaborative working scheme encourages a diversity of perspectives and expertise to work together to produce a powerful and impactful outcome that could not have been achieved

by these organisations working in isolation. However, one of the first challenges to be faced when trying to work in collaborative schemes is how to set up the working group and how to select the organisations.

Practical recommendations:

To form the group, it is important to locate and involve the appropriate organisations: that add value to the project, that are interested in being part of it and that have the resources to participate. Likewise, a "steering group" can be defined, but other organisations can be invited to collaborate in different phases of the project.

Although the quadruple helix is the ideal scheme, it is not mandatory. Organisations should be chosen according to their differential contribution to the project; the final composition of the group will depend on the specific objective of the project and the surrounding ecosystem. If it has not been done before, this may be a good time to involve civil society entities that can provide important insights on the problem and how to address it. In the case of TRANSFORM, the result of this reflection was that it was more aligned with the objectives to involve non-associated citizens in a later phase of the pilots, but this does not have to be the case for all projects.

Organisations are made up of people, some more motivated than others, some with more time than others. It is advisable to locate people within the organisation who show a real motivation to carry out this type of process.

8.2.2 Challenge 6: ensuring that the results of citizen science projects truly inform public policy

"One of the challenges of citizen participation in the field of public policy is the cultural change required to overcome all the resistance among scientists and professionals, but also other agents in the system who are used to delegating decisions to others."

Esther Vizcaíno. Researcher in the Health Research Area. Health Quality and Assessment Agency of Catalonia (AQuAS)

One of the challenges to be overcome throughout the project (and it was an objective from the beginning, not a challenge that appeared unexpectedly), was to ensure that the results

of the pilots were effectively used by the competent authorities to define/revise/improve their policies. There is a classic isolation between academic knowledge generation and policy making, which has traditionally prevented evidence-based policy making.

Citizen science, even though one of its foundations is precisely to have a policy impact, is not exempt from this inertia of other scientific disciplines, as explained in previous chapters; hence, although several studies demonstrate the potential of citizen science to inform policy, this potential is far from being fully realised.

In the case of the Catalan cluster in TRANSFORM, closing the circle between citizen science has been achieved thanks to specific strategies and actions. One of the keys for the success of the project and its impact on policies at local and regional levels has been to engage the organisations owning the challenges to be addressed in the whole process (framing the challenge, co-designing the project, implementing the project, monitoring the results, translating the results into action). If the entities responsible for taking action are not engaged from the beginning it will be much more difficult that they adopt the results, affecting the impact.

Practical recommendations:

To involve policy-makers (ot the actor that will be in charge of integrating the citizen science results) from the beginning in the co-design of the project, is a crucial step. It's also important to guarantee that the project responds to a real need or challenge expressed by the organisation that will be in charge of incorporating the results. Obviously, the research has to respect the necessary scientific rigour so that the results can be considered reliable. In case there are limitations or biases, just like in classical scientific disciplines, it is necessary to be very transparent and honest with it.

8.2.3 Challenge 7: finding the common objective

“The big challenge is to align interests that are very divergent. If they converge, the power is very strong. The strategy is to talk and listen to each other.”

Josep Perelló. Founding Director OpenSystemsUB

“Another challenge: finding this common goal. It is a job that has to be done iteratively, constantly throughout the project, not that you find it from the beginning and that's it. The

fact that some organisations are project partners and others are not, makes this even more important."

Diana Reinoso. Project manager at Science for Change

Each organisation has its own objectives and interests and has to respond to its own internal logics, plans, strategies, etc. Academia, public administration, companies, and within them also the different areas or departments, have different objectives. So do the citizenship itself and (given that it is not uniform) different social groups within it. Therefore, one of the biggest challenges when working collaboratively is to find the common goal that brings together the individual objectives. Only in this way will the different actors feel the project as their own. Moreover, this is not an exercise to be carried out only at the beginning of the project; throughout its development, the project goes through various phases that may "resonate" to some organisations more than to others, the priorities of the organisations themselves may vary or even, in real contexts, new objectives may emerge that change the course of the original idea.

Especially when it comes to inviting the public to participate, whose participation is not part of a working scheme, this is an even greater challenge. It is not always the case that objectives that we, as the driving force behind the project, find powerful enough to be relevant enough for the citizens to dedicate their free time to participate. In fact, we can often make the mistake of approaching citizens with the discourse of "our" objectives but without having done the exercise of reflecting on what interest citizens may have in participating in the project. This whole process has to be learned to be managed.

Practical recommendations:

In the process of involving stakeholders in the project (both at the beginning and throughout the project), it is useful to define specific engagement strategies that take into account the potential objectives and interests of the target stakeholders (put yourself in the mind of another). It is important also to devote the necessary time and effort, especially (but not only) during the first phases, to understand the objectives and interests of the other actors, in order to define a common objective that encompasses all the particulars and maintain this active listening over time.

Thirdly, it is highly advisable to draft and agree on a document where the objectives, the role of each actor and what each organisation hopes to achieve are reflected.

On the other hand, it is necessary to keep an open attitude to possible changes that may occur during the course of the project. It is important to create a climate of trust between group members so that each organisation feels comfortable to express when its interests are not being taken into account.

8.2.4 Challenge 8: finding the common language

“One of the challenges has been to get the different stakeholders talking, with their different languages and methodologies. That’s why we had to do research beforehand, to be able to understand the languages at the medical level and also at the protocol level, etc. This has also meant that we have had to bring the medical and protocol language closer to the people affected themselves: specifically in the exercise of drafting recommendations to improve public policies.”

Nora Salas Seoane, Head of the Health Area. Science for Change

“How do we communicate what we are doing? It is important to find an easy and not too technical language to communicate with citizens and schools.”

Albert del Amor. Former Programme Coordinator - Area of Open Government, Economic Development and Innovation, Mollet del Vallès city council

Another added challenge in this type of project is the different backgrounds and consequently the different languages used by the project agents. The level of specialisation promoted by the academy, in addition to its undeniable advantages, also generates a scientific jargon that has proven to be an element of alienation and "estrangement" of other actors regarding science; and not only of other actors but also of different disciplines within the academy. Although the academy may be the greatest exponent of this phenomenon, it is not the only one: all sectors develop their own languages, related to their technical profile, which are not understood or shared by others. Hence, in recent years the academy has been making efforts to promote scientific dissemination aimed at different targets, as part of its effort to bring science closer to society.

“Language” problems, therefore, do not only arise when it comes to contact with citizens; the partner actors themselves will encounter this challenge in their internal communication with each other.

One of the aspirations and potentialities of citizen science is to reduce this gap through 1) an adaptation of technical or scientific language to "non-professional" language and, 2) a process of scientific-technical literacy of both citizens and actors from other sectors. But, as in the previous cases, this process does not happen automatically and requires particular efforts.

Practical recommendations:

The collaborating actors should devote sufficient time and effort to familiarise themselves with the terminology of the other actors (share and read relevant documents, presentations, protocols, etc.).

Secondly, as an integral element of citizen science, one of the objectives of the project should be to increase citizens' (technical, scientific) knowledge or understanding of the specific topic (and if possible, of the scientific process itself).

In the opposite (but not contradictory) sense, specific communication strategies have to be designed to adapt the terminology (not to simplify) to the target audience.

8.2.5 Challenge 9: defining a common and realistic calendar

"Complexity: integrating all actors and their agendas and needs (citizenship, students, teachers, who all have different timetables; Final Degree Thesis, subjects, etc.)."

Xavier Ariño - Head of Institutional Projects - Rector's Office at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Each organisation participating in the project also has its own calendar to meet, which can easily generate "decoupling" between the necessary rhythms of the project (for issues such as budget or technical needs) and the calendars of the rest of the organisations. In the TRANSFORM citizen science pilots, this has been especially relevant in the case of collaboration with educational institutions of formal education (schools/institutes and universities). These institutions, and the students that are part of them, have to comply with a curriculum and with certain tasks (exams, final projects, practices) in a stricter way than other types of organisations. Although part of this curriculum and of these tasks can be used in a positive way to generate deeper collaborations with the actors (for example, when

students participate in the project through an internship or a Final Degree Project), they can also mean difficulties for the implementation of certain parts of the project or for the involvement of the students at certain moments of the investigation. Public administrations also have specific calendars (annual budget closures, political agenda, for example). As in the previous points, this is a fact that must be learned to manage.

To be as realistic as possible with the project's calendar, it must be borne in mind that in order to carry out any programmed activity, in practice third parties from each organisation will have to be involved (not only the people who are in the group). This inevitably slows down the procedures. If this is not taken into account from the beginning, the risk is that a schedule is planned that is too far removed from reality (which will have to be constantly adapted during the project, with the load of uncertainty that this entails) and also that perhaps some activities cannot be carried out because they have not begun to plan sufficiently in advance.

Practical recommendations:

Firstly, it is important to define from the beginning a tentative calendar of the different activities to be carried out throughout the project to have a first general vision of the fit of the calendars of each actor. If you intend to incorporate the collaboration of educational institutions, it is advisable to start the contact and make the proposal well in advance, bearing in mind that, in addition to this project, educational institutions participate in other activities and collaborate with other agents.

On the other hand, it is advisable to plan the calendar in a realistic and flexible manner, defining how much time in advance the activities should start to be organised.

8.2.6 Challenge 10: managing the uncertainties and changes

“With other projects you have a more defined plan; in this project we have been co-designing, co-building the project from the beginning. In this context, you always have to bear in mind that this means that some opportunities fall through, and you have to calculate and manage this (even at an emotional level), but it also means that many new opportunities arise. The fact that there are so many different organisations has a multiplier effect.”

Diana Reinoso. TRANSFORM Project Manager, Science for Change

Despite the fact that in every project there are usually deviations from the initial planning, in a single leadership work scheme, which is more linear, this factor is not as relevant as in collaborative work schemes. As the development of activities does not depend on a single person or organisation but on many, it is difficult to have control of all the variables that may affect the project. Some planned activities may not be possible to implement in the end, but also other new opportunities may arise. Also, collaborative work schemes are usually iterative; each new step can make previous approaches reformulate or can generate new needs (for example, involving actors that were not initially planned).

Figures 4 and 5. Differences between a single leadership and a collaborative working scheme

Practical recommendations:

Despite having an initial calendar, projects that involve the collaboration of so many different actors, it is easy for them to suffer changes in calendar. These can be mostly delays, but unexpected events can also arise that require advances. As in previous points, it is important to maintain an open and resilient attitude towards this, and be proactive.

8.2.7 Challenge 11: coordinating the group to avoid chaos

“The coordination itself: different actors in different buildings, with different agendas. A lot of formality is needed, to have regular meetings, to write minutes of these meetings, etc. Also the fact that we don't know each other, we have to work on everything online.”

Diana Reinoso Botsho. Project Manager, Science for Change

In this type of project in which so many different agents participate, one of the most important challenges is internal coordination. It must be taken into account that each organisation is physically in a different place, with different logistics, has different tasks and each actor participates in turn in other activities. This inevitably generates a tendency to entropy that, if not managed, can put the trust between the actors and the project itself at risk.

The success factor in managing this challenge has been the establishment of minimal formal procedures, always open to any changes that may arise.

Practical recommendations:

It is highly recommended that internal coordination is defined as a specific task and that it is assumed by a single organisation/person. Some coordination subtasks can be distributed, but it is important that this organisation/person is ultimately responsible and that the rest of the actors identify it as such. It is also highly recommended to leave the meeting dates fixed from the beginning for months to come so that all the actors have those time slots reserved.

Finally, it is highly recommended to make a minutes document of each meeting, to reflect what was discussed and the agreements reached.

8.2.8 Challenge 12: facilitating the dialogue process

“Sometimes we find it hard to do things differently, this project forces us to come up with innovative solutions, to do things the way we don't usually do them. SfC's work as a facilitator helps us to make decisions and find these innovative solutions.”

Albert del Amor. Former Programme Coordinator - Area of Open Government, Economic Development and Innovation, Mollet del Vallès city council

In addition to internal coordination, this type of project implies deploying a long process of dialogue and a permanent search for consensus. This is not a process that necessarily occurs naturally and specific time and skills are needed to ensure it.

Practical recommendations:

As in the previous case, it is highly recommended that an organisation/person take on the task of facilitating collaborative processes. It can be (but not necessarily), the same organisation/person that is in charge of the coordination. It implies that this organisation/person must have a general vision of the project and of the objectives and tasks of all the actors involved. In addition, this person must implement certain "soft skills" such as patience, tolerance to changes, flexibility, active listening and resilience.

8.3 Action practice: doing citizen science

The challenges and recommendations that are reported below refer to the development of the citizen science project itself.

8.3.1 Challenge 13: addressing both the scientific and the social and educational slopes of the project

As explained in section 2, citizen science is governed by compliance with 10 principles, which involve scientific, social impact, ethical, educational, political and even environmental aspects. Attending so many different elements is not usual in the development of R&I projects and this constitutes both the greatest potential but also the greatest risk of failure of a citizen science project. In some projects, a lot of effort may be devoted to the social or educational aspect but the scientific requirements are neglected. In others, the focus may be on scientific rigour and citizens are treated solely as generators of data, neglecting ethical aspects or the necessary care that must be deployed to be responsible and transparent with citizens.

Practical recommendations:

There are various manuals of good practices in citizen science and it is not the objective of this document to reproduce their content. However, some practical recommendations can be extracted from the TRANSFORM experience.

One of the keys to ensuring that all aspects of citizen science are properly addressed is the very diversity of the actors that are part of the project and their different backgrounds. For example, academia will generally provide the necessary methodologies, protocols, and

validation methods to ensure scientific rigour; civil society organisations will ensure that the project meets the needs and expectations of society or the specific group in society they represent; the educational institutions will guarantee that the project fulfils the expected educational or training work that it has been proposed; etc.

In addition, it is also very important to have an expert organisation/person specifically in citizen science who has knowledge of the usual citizen science practices applicable at different times of the project and who guarantees that no aspect is being forgotten.

8.3.2 Challenge 14: ensuring citizen engagement

“Another challenge is the involvement of the institutes: each one has its own agenda, when we have opened up the possibility of collaboration, some have joined directly, but others have not seen it as necessary. We have to make a strategy.”

Albert del Amor. Former Programme Coordinator - Area of Open Government, Economic Development and Innovation, Mollet del Vallès city council

We may have designed the most interesting project from the R&I point of view and that does not mean that the public considers it interesting or that they are willing to spend part of their free time collaborating. One of the greatest challenges facing citizen science is precisely to involve citizens.

Practical recommendations:

In order to involve citizens, it is very important, first of all, to define which profiles of citizens you want/need to involve and how much. Based on these profiles, specific strategies must be developed to target them, taking into account, for example, what media these people use and what events they usually attend. It is also important to define in which phases you want to involve the public. It is not the same to ask for a specific collaboration that implies a short time, than to demand a long-term collaboration. Depending on these variables, strategies will have to be defined, but always bearing in mind that a lot of effort will have to be dedicated to achieving this participation and maintaining it overtime if necessary.

Another very relevant element, as mentioned above, is to reflect on what interest citizens may have in contributing to the project and design the engagement strategy taking this into account, not only for the creation of messages but also to be able to comply with those objectives throughout the project. If citizens feel that their expectations are not being met or

that they are not being treated correctly, the associated frustration will reduce their willingness to continue collaborating with our project and probably with any other project of this nature in the future.

In this sense, it is also very important not to create false expectations among citizens. Many times, the will that projects have to mobilise changes at the political level, for example, means that citizens are promised that certain changes will actually take place when perhaps that final decision is not in the hands of the members of the steering group of the project. It's necessary to be honest and transparent with this.

One of the success factors for sustaining participation is to make citizens feel part of the project. This is mainly achieved by informing participants on a regular basis (via e-mail or other means) about the progress of the project and by planning an adequate feedback of the results.

8.3.3 Challenge 15: ensuring diversity and inclusiveness

Another of the promises of citizen science is that it allows all kinds of people to be included in the process of generating knowledge and formulating public policies, including people who are normally excluded from these processes. However, as in previous aspects, this is not something that occurs naturally. The greatest risk is that in the process of involving citizens, only people with a high socioeconomic and socio-educational level, who are usually the most interested and knowledgeable about science and R&I, feel challenged by our call. It is also quite likely that migrants, people with functional diversity, etc. will be left out.

This was the case of the endometriosis pilot: although the level of engagement and commitment of the citizen scientists was very high (a fact that usually occurs in the case of health projects since the participants feel directly challenged because they are the ones that suffer from the disease or its consequences), it is true that the fact of using social networks for recruitment generated a bias in the type of participants (at the socio-educational level). This aspect is expected to be improved in future developments.

The strategy used in the waste pilot, however, was successful in guaranteeing inclusiveness and diversity, as explained below.

Practical recommendations:

As in the previous case, it is necessary to define specific strategies to ensure inclusivity, which have to do with adapting messages and approaching places and events that people with different profiles tend to attend. Communication through social networks tends to delve into bias, which is why it will often be necessary to develop direct contact strategies with certain groups. For this reason, in this case it is recommended (something that could not be done in the TRANSFORM endometriosis pilot due to lack of time) to define a specific strategy to approach underrepresented groups (and reserve time and resources to implement it).

The strategy followed in the waste pilot has been to work with public schools. People from different socioeconomic levels and from different backgrounds are represented in public schools, and therefore help us ensure that a diversity of voices are represented and have the opportunity to benefit from participation in the project. Another of the strategies that is useful to implement is to involve the participation department of the municipalities. These departments have in-depth knowledge of civil society in their municipality and serve as direct access to a variety of groups.

8.3.4 Challenge 16: Mainstreaming gender

Last but not least, it is nowadays compulsory to take into account the gender perspective and the gender bias in R&I and citizen science projects. Both pilots have ensured that gender balance and gender mainstreaming was met both in terms of participants and within the language and communication messages as well as in the construction of the project itself in all its phases. In particular, the woman's health pilot is a pilot that aims to raise awareness of the necessity of mainstreaming gender in health to overcome the gender bias in biomedical research. Endometriosis would not be infra diagnosed if it would affect both women and men, unfortunately - even if it affects 10% of women globally. Women have been underrepresented in biomedical research and treated differently in healthcare facilities - affecting the way their health is comprehended.

Practical recommendations:

Ensure you can adapt your project to meet gender balance and mainstream gender.

You can use those guides [Gendered Innovations](#), for instance, in order to inspire and support you.

It is important to plan your actions and think in terms of gender beforehand - in particular taking into account stakeholder mapping and stakeholder engagement. Moreover, it is important to mainstream gender in the language and design you use for your communication strategies. Therefore, the recommendation would be to think and create your project wearing gender glasses.

Annex 1. Citizen science and increased knowledge through gamification: Dilemma R

Pictures 22, 23. Images of the waste game

Is it possible to reflect on waste management and collect information from citizens by playing games? Serious games and gamification allow reflection on real problems in fictitious scenarios and makes it possible to collect information-based citizens' opinions. To achieve this objectives, Science for Change codesigned the waste game "Dilemma R" introducing gamification as a way to 1) increase citizen knowledge on municipal waste management

systems and, 2) to collect their opinions and preferences. The game was designed in *minecraft* style to make it more appealing to the public. In order to give a reward, it was defined with the municipality that playing the game would have a compensation in the reduction of the waste management tax.

The game has these different components:

- **Data protection and legal aspects:** before starting to play, citizens are provided with information about the project and information about the data protection policy. The citizen has to give his or her consent to enter the game.
- **Choosing the avatar and sociodemographic questions:** questions typical of sociological surveys in order to be able to track differences between different social profiles.

Age, gender, educational level, neighbourhood, family structure, housing type

Picture 24. Image of the waste game

- **Game approach:** the avatar (citizen) meets the fictitious environmental technician of the town, who tells her that the town council is going to change the waste management system in order to increase the percentage of selective waste collection. However, the municipality wants to know the opinion of the citizens before making a decision. Therefore, the avatar is asked to talk to different people in the town to gather their opinions.
- **4 scenarios with 7 dilemmas:** In each scenario, the avatar encountered two typical characters from a village (shopkeeper, elderly person, university student, etc.). Between these characters, a debate was established in which divergent positions were being shown on the following issue: pros and cons of the door to door system and

the smart containers regarding environmental, practical and economic variables. Cons were always expressed in an open and transparent manner.

Picture 25. Image of the waste game

- **Preference question, Dilemma:** after each dialog the avatar (citizen) had to express his or her preference. This preference is expressed in the form of a dilemma in which choosing one option excludes choosing the other.

Picture 26. Image of the waste game

- **Prior knowledge questions and final QUIZ:** In order to be able to evaluate whether the avatar (citizen) has indeed increased his level of knowledge about waste management, he is asked 3 questions at the beginning of the game. At the end of the game a QUIZ of three questions (related to the first ones) is asked.

Picture 27. Image of the waste game

- **Final preference question, door-to-door vs. smart containers:** at the end, after having evaluated different positive and negative aspects of each innovative separate collection system, the avatar was asked about his or her favourite system.
- **Collect personal data:** after playing the game and repeating the objective of collecting personal data (reduction in the waste rate), the avatar (citizen) is asked for his/her name, surname and ID card number, this information being voluntary.

Reflections on the success of the game:

After the analysis of the process and taking into account both the observation and the objective measurement of the QUIZ, we can say the following:

- **Adaptability to different audiences:** the game explains technical issues but in a simple way, so it is easy to understand for different audiences. However, the work of the students was very much appreciated in the case of older people, for whom it was helpful for the student to explain the dialogues and make the process more dynamic.
- **Duration of the game:** although the game took on average 15 minutes to complete (which is a long time for a game that has to be played in the street), it was found that this duration was not excessive for most people, especially because of the interaction with the pupils who helped to make it dynamic. The difficulty of providing knowledge on such a complex subject and promoting reflection in less time can also be

considered. The game was particularly successful with individuals or couples with children in the playgrounds, as they were mostly seated, and in the case of several people, the game generated a very fruitful and interesting debate between them.

- **Increased knowledge:** thanks to the comparison between the prior knowledge questions and the final QUIZ, the success of this aspect could be verified. The results showed that of the people who had answered no knowledge in the initial questions, an average of 75% were correct in the QUIZ answers.

Picture 28. Image of the waste game

- **Waste rate reduction as an incentive:** it could be seen that this element was not particularly motivating, probably because 1) it was not a high incentive (playing the game was not directly equivalent to a reduction in the rate but to 1 point out of 10 to qualify for this reduction) and 2) it implied having to provide personal data, which many people were reluctant to do.
- **Gamification element:** another element to improve is the gamification approach itself. From observation, it was found that the approach to the situation and the final objective was not very appealing, so this element could be improved.

Annex 2: educational material

The training session with the secondary students lasted 5 hours (with a 0.5 hour break in between) and covered the following topics:

- What is citizen science? (given by a member of the Catalan cluster).
- State of waste management in Mollet del Vallès (given by environmental technicians from the city council).
- How the waste game has been created? (given by the team of the external company expert in game development).
- What are statistics and how will we use them in this project? (given by a member of the Catalan cluster)

Below, we share the materials used for the topic “What are statistics and how will we use them in this project?”, so that it can be reused by others.

**Què és això de l'estadística
i com la farem servir?**

TRANSFORM

TRANSFORM

De què en parlarem avui...

1. Què és això de l'estadística?
2. Conceptes clau
3. Mostra representativa. Càlcul
4. Diversitat
5. Tipus de gràfics
6. Que farem a Mollet

TRANSFORM

2

Què és això de l'estadística?

Branca de la matemàtica que utilitza grans conjunts de dades numèriques per a obtenir inferències basades en el càlcul de probabilitats

TRANSFORM

3

Què és això de l'estadística?

Branca de la matemàtica que utilitza grans conjunts de dades numèriques per a obtenir inferències basades en el càlcul de probabilitats

Descriptiva

Inferencial

TRANSFORM

4

Què és això de l'estadística?

Branca de la matemàtica que utilitza grans conjunts de dades numèriques per a obtenir inferències basades en el càlcul de probabilitats

Descriptiva

Inferencial

TRANSFORM

5

Què és això de l'estadística?

L'estadística **descriptiva** és una disciplina que s'encarrega de recollir, emmagatzemar, ordenar, realitzar taules o gràfics i calcular **paràmetres bàsics** sobre el conjunt de dades.

TRANSFORM

6

Conceptes clau

Variables Qualitatives: Fa referència a una qualitat. Exemples: el color d'ulls d'una persona o el color del cabell.

Variables Quantitatives: Fa referència a una mesura quantitativa. Exemples: l'altura d'una persona en centímetres o les notes dels alumnes d'una classe.

TRANSFORM

7

Conceptes clau

- **Població:** Conjunt total d'elements objecte d'estudi
Example: Ciutadania de Mollet del Vallès
- **Mostra:** Part de la població que se selecciona per poder fer afirmacions sobre el total de la població objecte d'estudi

TRANSFORM

8

Conceptes clau

- **Població:** Conjunt total d'elements objecte d'estudi
Example: Ciutadania de Mollet del Vallès
- **Mostra:** Part de la població que se selecciona per poder fer afirmacions sobre el total de la població objecte d'estudi

Però, quina quantitat es necessita???

TRANSFORM

9

Què és una mostra representativa?

Grup de població que reflecteix amb precisió el total de la població.

Dependrà de:

- Grandària de la població
- La precisió que vulguem

Sense representativitat, les dades que recollim no seran “estadísticament” vàlides

TRANSFORM

10

Càlcul mostra representativa

Cómo calcular el tamaño de muestra para una población finita

$$n = \frac{N * Z_{\alpha}^2 * p * q}{e^2 * (N - 1) + Z_{\alpha}^2 * p * q}$$

n = Tamaño de muestra buscado

N = Tamaño de la Población o Universo

z = Parámetro estadístico que depende el Nivel de Confianza (NC)

e = Error de estimación máximo aceptado

p = Probabilidad de que ocurra el evento estudiado (éxito)

q = (1 - p) = Probabilidad de que no ocurra el evento estudiado

TRANSFORM

11

Què és una mostra representativa?

A calcular!!

Nivell de confiança: 95% o 99%
Marge d'error: màxim 5% (0,05)

TRANSFORM

12

i per barris?

A calcular!!

Barris	Homes	Dones	Població	% Total
Barri dels Col·legis Nous	4.023	4.227	8.250	16,12
Barri de Can Pantiquet	2.922	3.061	5.983	11,69
Barri de la Riera Seca	1.261	1.316	2.577	5,04
Barri de la Zona Centre	2.694	2.871	5.565	10,87
Barri de l'Estació de França	2.845	2.971	5.816	11,36
Barri del Calderí	963	989	1.952	3,81
Barri de l'Estació del Nord	2.409	2.473	4.882	9,54
Barri de Can Borrell	3.000	3.102	6.102	11,92
Barri de la Plana Lledó	3.585	3.457	7.042	13,76
Barri de Santa Rosa	981	985	1.966	3,84
Poligon Industrial de la Farinera	0	0	0	0,00
Poligon Industrial de Can Prat	2	2	4	0,01
Barri de la Casilla	12	20	32	0,06
Poligon Industrial de Can Magarola	1	3	4	0,01
Àrea del Tir Olímpic	17	10	27	0,05
Barri de Lourdes	420	436	856	1,67
Gallecs	65	52	117	0,23
TOTALS	25.200	25.975	51.175	100,00

TRANSFORM

13

Més enllà de la representativitat numérica...

La mostra ha de representar la diversitat

Grupos de edad	
2021	
De 0 a 14 años	7.474
De 15 a 64 años	34.576
De 65 a 84 años	7.835
De 85 años y más	1.266
Total	51.151

Click to add text

Población a 1 de enero. Por sexo y edad quinquenal. Mollet del Vallès. 2021

Fuente: Idescat, a partir del Padrón continuo del INE.

TRANSFORM

14

Més enllà de la representativitat numérica...

Nacionalidad	
2021	
Española	45.157
Extranjera	5.994
Total	51.151

tabla ampliada

Población a 1 de enero. Por nacionalidad (continentes) y sexo Mollet del Vallès. 2021

	Española	Resto de la Unión Europea	Resto de Europa	África	América del Norte y Central	América del Sur	Asia y Oceanía	Total
Hombres	22.042	525	230	1.182	112	741	348	25.180
Mujeres	23.115	475	253	721	208	899	300	25.971
Total	45.157	1.000	483	1.903	320	1.640	648	51.151

Click to add text Fuente: Idescat, a partir del Padrón continuo del INE.

TRANSFORM

CSV

Más tablas >

15

Més enllà de la representativitat numérica...

Nivel de formación alcanzado

2019 (p) (%)

CAT COM MUN

Educación primaria o inferior	20,3
Primera etapa de educación secundaria	33,5
Segunda etapa de educación secundaria	22,1
Educación superior	24,2

tabla ampliada

Click to add text

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Més enllà de la representativitat numérica...

Tipología de los hogares

2011

CAT COM MUN

Una persona	3.462
Dos personas o más sin núcleo	463
Pareja sin hijos	4.472
Pareja con hijos	8.167
Padre o madre con hijos	2.341
Dos núcleos o más	401
Total	19.307

Gráficos tabla ampliada

Click to add text

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On ens posarem?

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Quines dades analitzarem?

Variables

- 1) variables sociodemogràfiques (7)
- 2) coneixement previ (2)
- 3) QUIZ coneixement després d'haver jugat (3)
- 4) respostes als dilemes plantejats al llarg del joc (decisiones entre dues opcions) (7)
- 5) Per a cada dilema i ha una pregunta de comprovació (nivell de seguretat en la resposta) (7).
- 6) Preferència per un sistema o l'altre (1)

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Quines dades analitzarem?

Objectiu a: informar a la ciutadania:

- Grau de coneixement previ dels sistemes innovadors de recollida selectiva (1 pregunta)
- Grau de coneixement previ del percentatge de recollida selectiva de Mollet (1)
- Coneixement després d'haver jugat al joc (3 preguntes: QUIZ)

Quines dades analitzarem?

Objectiu b: Esbrinar la preferència general pel sistema de contenidors intel·ligents o el porta a porta

- Creuament de les variables sociodemogràfiques amb
- preferència pel sistema de contenidors intel·ligents o el porta a porta (1 pregunta)

Quines dades analitzarem?

Objectiu c: Descriure quines variables són més rellevants per a cada tipologia de persona.

- Creuament de les variables sociodemogràfiques amb
- dilemes

Com analitzarem les dades?

Distribució de freqüències: forma en la qual un conjunt de dades es classifica en diferents grups excloents entre si. És a dir, si una dada pertany a un grup no pot pertànyer a un altre.

- **Freqüència absoluta:** quantitat d'observacions que pertanyen a cada grup.
- **Freqüència relativa:** mesura estadística que es calcula com el quocient de la freqüència absoluta d'algun valor de la població/mostra entre el total de valors que componen la població/mostra.

S

Tipus de gràfics

Diagrama de barres

Una variable

Dos variables

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Tipus de gràfics

Gràfic circular o per sectors

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Després, jugarem amb els gràfics... i extraurem conclusions

Enquesta de Satisfacció Municipal

Nom de Municipi

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